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Deliverable 4.3

Final design of intelligent orchestration and management mechanisms

Abstract

D4.3 is the third deliverable within DAEMON WP4 documents, hence building on D4.1 and D4.2, and focusing on NI-based solutions for service and resource orchestration and management. This deliverable outlines the final design of 14 NI solutions distributed across four WP tasks: energy-aware VNF orchestration, capacity forecasting, automated anomaly detection, and self-learning MANO. The document offers a high-level overview of these solutions, their alignment with the DAEMON architecture in WP2, and planned WP5 experiments for validation. Each NI solution is detailed with a WP2 requirement mapping and architectural insights, concluding with future directions of how the WP4 footprint relates to the ongoing activities on the next generation of mobile networks.

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	– 3rd Generation Partnership Project
AAS	– Average Anomaly Score
AC	– Admission Control
AF	– Application Function
AI	– Artificial Intelligence
AIRIC	– AI-driven Radio Intelligent Controller
API	– Application Programming Interface
B5G	– Beyond 5G
BBU	– Base Band Unit
BIC	– Bayesian Information Criterion
CFORE	– Capacity Forecasting
CPU	– Central Processing Unit
CQI	– Channel Quality Indicator
CSOI	– Creation Selection Optimization and Instantiation
CU	– Central Unit
DC	– Datacenter
DDQL	– Double Deep Q-Learning
DL	– Downlink
DMARL	– Distributed Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning
DQN	– Deep Q-Network
DRL	– Deep Reinforcement Learning
DU	– Distributed Unit
EAWVNF	– Energy-Aware VNF control & orchestration
EDAF	– Edge-Deployment Alternatives Finder
ENI	– Experiential Networked Intelligence
FL	– Federated Learning
FR	– Functional Requirement
GP	– Gaussian Process
GPU	– Graphics Processing Unit
IoT	– Internet of Things
iTarea	– Energy-Efficient Task and Resource Allocator
KNF	– Kubernetes-based Network Functions
KPI	– Key Performance Indicator
LCB	– Lower Confidence Bound
LDV	– Local Density Variance
LFU	– Least Frequently Used
LRU	– Least Recently Used
LSTM	– Long Short-Term Memory
MAC	– Medium Access Control
MANO	– Management and Orchestration
MAPE-K	– Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute over a shared Knowledge
MCS	– Modulation and Coding Scheme
MDAF	– Management Data Analytics Function
MILP	– Mixed Integer Linear Program
ML	– Machine Learning
MNO	– Mobile Network Operators
NDF	– New Devices Finder
NF	– Network Function
NFR	– Non-functional Requirement
NFVI	– Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NFVO	– Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
NI	– Network Intelligence

NIF – Network Intelligence Function
NIF-C – Network Intelligence Function Component
NIFD – Network Intelligence Function Descriptor
NIO – Network Intelligence Orchestrator
NIP – Network Intelligence Plane
NIS – Network Intelligence Service
NISD – Network Intelligence Service Descriptor
NO – Network Orchestrator
NSSI – Network Slice Subnet Instance
OCO – Online Convex Optimization
OPEX – Operating Expenses
OSM – Open Source MANO
PHY – Physical Layer
PM – Physical Machine
PoE – Power over Ethernet
PolicyIC – Policy Interpreter and Configuration
PTP – Precision Time Protocol
QoE – Quality of Experience
RA – Resource Allocation
RAM – Random Access Memory
RAN – Radio Access Network
RB – Resource Block
RIC – Radio Intelligent Controller
RL – Reinforcement Learning
RN – Relation Network
RR – Resource Reservation
RU – Remote Unit
SAIR – Send Authentication Information Request
SFC – Service Function Chain
SLA – Service Level Agreement
SMO – Service and Management Orchestration
SNR – Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SP – Service Provider
SVM – Support Vector Machine
TPC – Transmission Power Control
UL – Uplink
VAE – Variational Autoencoder
vBS – Virtual Base Station
VIM – Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM – Virtual Machine
VNF – Virtual Network Function
vRAN – Virtual RAN
WP – Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the advancements achieved by the DAEMON project in crafting and creating Network Intelligence (NI)-assisted functionalities tailored for Beyond Fifth Generation (B5G) mobile networks, with a specific concentration on the domain of service and resource management as well as orchestration. In pursuit of this overarching objective, we explore four critical B5G functionalities, namely:

1. Energy aware Virtual Network Function (VNF) orchestration
2. Capacity forecasting
3. Automated anomaly detection
4. Self-learning MANagement and Orchestration (MANO)

As the final deliverable of a series, D4.3 builds on the results of D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2] and provides detailed information on fourteen (14) NI-assisted functionalities, where eleven (11) of the problems were introduced in D4.1 [1] and three (3) additional problems were introduced in D4.2 [2].

Starting from Section 3, we present the latest advancements in NI-assisted functionalities. We provide technical descriptions for each of these functionalities and discuss their integration with the NI procedures defined in D2.3 [3], including how the Network Intelligence Functions (NIFs) leverage interfaces within the NI orchestration framework. We also offer practical examples of how the NIFs incorporate these procedures. Furthermore, we provide updates on compliance with the specified requirements.

In detail, Section 3 discusses energy-aware VNF orchestration solutions, addressing different network levels with four (4) solutions, including user/data-level Network Function (NF) placement and scaling and Radio Access Network (RAN)-level NFs. These solutions utilize varied algorithms and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, optimizing energy consumption, throughput, and service-specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Proceeding to Section 4, we delve into capacity forecasting methods that anticipate resource needs before actual demand. D4.3 introduces four (4) solutions in this context. These solutions employ advanced techniques such as time-series forecasting, meta-learning, and hybrid learning to improve resource allocation efficiency. They address functionality requirements from D2.3 [3] and surpass traditional AI/Machine Learning (ML) approaches, tackling issues like slow convergence in online learning algorithms and suboptimal predefined loss functions.

In Section 5, we outline DAEMON's progress in automated anomaly response. This section introduces four (4) solutions for identifying anomalies across different cellular network components, including RAN, base stations, and international mobile operator connections.

In Section 6, we explore self-learning MANO solutions, which play a pivotal role in the complexity of B5G networks' decision-making processes. We introduce two (2) solutions, which are crucial given the diverse and intricate operational decisions involved.

Prior to our conclusion in Section 8, we explore in Section 7 how WP4 activities align with ongoing trends in standardization efforts towards 6G.

In Section 8, we provide closing remarks summarizing the essential findings of this deliverable.

1 Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to report on the progress made by Work Package 4 (WP4) towards designing NI-based solutions for service and resource orchestration and management. Specifically, WP4 focuses on DAEMON's objective 2, which involves developing specialized NI-assisted network functionalities for 5G systems, as well as specific KPIs of objective 4, demonstrating the viability and performance of NI-native 5G networks. In this deliverable, we provide an overview of the updates to the solutions described in the previous deliverable, D4.2 [2], and their interrelationships. We also establish mappings between these solutions and the requirements and architecture proposed in D2.3 [3]. This deliverable presents fourteen (14) solutions, where (i) four (4) solve the problem of energy-aware VNF orchestration, (ii) four (4) solve the problem of capacity forecasting, (iii) four (4) solve the problem of automated anomaly detection, and (iv) two (2) solve the problem of self-learning MANO.

This deliverable is structured as follows. First, in this section, subsection 1.1, we summarize the improvements made to the solutions described in D4.2 [2]. The next section focuses on reconciling the perspectives of WP2 and WP4. We strive to align the architectural viewpoint represented by the Network Intelligence Orchestrator (NIO) components with the detailed design of each solution. We identify a scenario that illustrates how two specific WP4 NIFs, namely BSvBS (Section 3.3) and HADES (Section 3.1), leverage the knowledge-sharing procedure defined in D2.3 [3] to improve the solutions.

The subsequent sections delve into detailed descriptions of each contribution. Each subsection follows a consistent structure:

- Solution description: describes the approach taken by a concrete solution, including its internal implementation and detailed design. If a solution has been fully described in D4.1 [1] or D4.2 [2], we include only a reference to the relevant deliverable. The achieved advances and new results are reported in detail in this section.
- Integration with the NI native procedures: describes the relation between the solution description and the NI native procedure described in D2.3 [3] and explains the integration of WP4 solutions into the NI plane described in WP2.
- Requirement satisfaction: presents the requirement satisfactions of the solutions and explains the rationale of how the specific solution addresses the requirements.

Therefore, we believe that the traceability between the solutions developed in WP4, their integration with the architecture defined in WP2, and the requirements can be easily followed through the integration and requirement subsections. We include all the solutions developed by DAEMON partners from the beginning of the project. Even the solutions that have been fully described in D4.1 [1] or D4.2 [2] are incorporated into this document, with their description completed by mapping them to integration and requirements. Prior to conclusions, we discuss how the solutions in D4.3 align with the ongoing efforts in establishing 6G standards. Finally, a conclusion section summarizes the contributions of this deliverable.

1.1 Overview of updates on WP4 solutions

A thorough overview of the WP4 solutions and the big picture of how the solutions fit into the DAEMON's NI plane is described in D4.2 [2]. Here, we give updates on improved solution descriptions. This deliverable includes ten solution improvements on top of D4.2 [2].

The problem of energy-aware VNF orchestration (WP4, task 4.1) has three improved solutions described in S3.1, S3.3, and S3.4. The solution S3.1 improved with a renewed architecture that includes a new energy model and a new forecasting algorithm utilizing Gradient Boosting Trees. The solution S3.3 contains two new algorithms leveraging bandit learning and meta-learning approaches. The solution S3.4 is improved to capture new realistic scenarios using a novel cost function.

There are two solution improvements in the problem of capacity forecasting (WP4, task 4.2) described in S4.1 and S4.4. The solution in S4.1 defines two new approaches for optimizing admission control and resource reservation jointly, and the solution in S4.4 is improved to allocate discrete decisions and non-convex optimization algorithms.

Regarding the anomaly detection works (WP4, task 4.3), there are three updated solutions described in S5.1, S5.2, and S5.4. The solution S5.1 addresses the challenges faced in D4.2 [2], such as agent-controller synchronization, signaling efficiency and agent-based rule-based classification optimization. Solution S5.2 is improved by using feature engineering to increase performance, and solution S5.4 includes a new approach that utilizes Relation Networks (RN) and Deep Q-Networks (DQN).

The problem of self-learning MANO (WP4, task 4.4) has two updated solutions described in S6.1 and S6.2. The solution S6.1 details the collaboration between the two approaches described in Section 6.1 of D4.1 [1] and in Section 5.1 of D4.2 [2], while the solution S6.2 defines a new reward function.

2 Native integration of WP4 algorithms in the WP2 architecture

D2.3 [3] defined the final version of the DAEMON project NI Native architecture and the procedures that constitute the way of interacting with the architecture. While in Sections 3, 4, 5, and 6, we detail how every NIF defined in WP4 leverages the different interfaces and architectural modules, in the following we discuss: (i) the fulfillment of the generic requirements from the architectural point of view towards the WP4 specificities, and (ii) the possible implementations of some guidelines specified in WP2 about the knowledge sharing between the different NIFs to improve the performance of the solutions.

2.1 Native integration of WP4 Algorithms in the DAEMON architecture from WP2

The NIFs targeted by WP4 target the integration of NI for service and resource management and orchestration, which operate in near-real-time or non-real-time timescales.

Figure 1. The Network Intelligence Plane (NIP) and the functional blocks of the NIO and ML pipelines [3].

Figure 1 provides a graphical depiction of the fundamental functional blocks prescribed by the DAEMON architecture. These blocks have been purposefully crafted to facilitate the seamless incorporation of NI into network operations. In the ensuing discussion, we will delve into an in-depth examination of how these specific components are applied within the solutions outlined in WP4.

2.1.1 ML Pipeline

The ML procedures play a vital role in preparing data-driven models that enable the implementation of various functionalities envisioned by the project. From the perspective of WP4, this aspect must consider the following key characteristics:

- ML procedures in the case of self-learning MANO should be explainable and trustworthy and can operate with minimal human intervention.
- ML procedures in case of capacity forecast should operate on different timescales and provide information about their accuracy.

2.1.2 Network Intelligence Orchestrator

The NIO assumes a crucial role in streamlining the effective management of network intelligence throughout the DAEMON project’s lifecycle. Collaborating closely with the NIF Managers and the NIF Component Manager, responsible for tasks like container management for individual intelligence components, the NIO encompasses multiple modules of utmost significance within the context of WP4.

2.1.2.1 Knowledge Management

The **knowledge management** component plays a vital role in facilitating effective MANO-NIO interactions within the network architecture. It ensures the planning, organization, action, and control of

knowledge across all deployed Network Intelligence Services (NISs). In the context of MANO-NIO interactions, knowledge management enables seamless communication and exchange of information between the two entities, enhancing the overall performance and efficiency of the network.

Within the MANO framework, the NIO collaborates with various components to synchronize network slices and functions, track their state and health, and gather real-time information about available resources. This synchronization and exchange of information enable the NIO to dynamically adapt decisions and optimize network operations based on up-to-date knowledge. By maintaining a synchronized view of resource availability, including computing power, storage, and network characteristics, the NIO can efficiently orchestrate network resources and allocate them to network slices, functions, or specific vertical service requirements. This dynamic resource management optimizes resource utilization and enhances overall performance.

Moreover, the NIO interacts with vertical service providers, establishing effective communication channels to exchange information, feedback, and service-specific instructions. This ensures that the orchestrated network intelligence aligns with the objectives and needs of vertical service domains, ultimately enhancing service delivery and improving the user's Quality of Experience (QoE).

In summary, the knowledge management component within the NIO enables effective MANO-NIO interactions by ensuring the synchronization of network slices and functions, real-time information exchange about available resources, and collaboration with vertical service providers. This facilitates seamless communication and knowledge sharing and enhances the overall performance and reliability of the network architecture.

2.1.2.2 NIS creation, selection, optimization and instantiation

The MANO-NIO interactions utilize the **NIS creation, selection, optimization, and instantiation** components to facilitate the deployment of NIS within the network architecture. This component is responsible for selecting the appropriate NIS based on hardware constraints, optimizing the NIS to achieve a desired tradeoff between model size and performance, and instantiating the selected NIS. If a required NIS is not available in the catalog, the component also has the capability to create it based on available data and execution context information.

In the context of MANO-NIO interactions, the NIO leverages this component to enable the creation, selection, optimization, and instantiation of a NIS. For instance, consider the example where a new Internet of Things (IoT) client purchases a managed connectivity service from the IoT platform. In order to provide proactive anomaly detection and improved service to the client, the operator deploys ANCHOR (S5.2), which requires a model capable of predicting anomalies for the cluster of devices in the client's IoT vertical.

In this scenario, the NIO initiates the NIS creation procedure since the IoT devices are new and not found in the catalog. The NIO triggers a request to retrieve the cluster corresponding to the IoT devices through the Nio-MLp interface. It communicates important characteristics of the IoT devices that have been observed over a 24-hour period, allowing the ANCHOR pipeline to determine the per-device cluster and utilize models trained for those respective clusters.

Upon training, the model is registered in the catalog and made available to the NIO via the MLOps pipeline through the MLp-Ncat and Nio-MLp interfaces. Finally, the NIO makes the NIS/NIF images available to the applicable NIF Component Manager using the Nio-Nifm interface.

This specific example highlights how the MANO-NIO interactions utilize the **NIS creation, selection, optimization, and instantiation** components to deploy NIS in response to specific service requirements. The NIO effectively communicates and coordinates with the various interfaces and components involved in the process, ensuring the availability of the necessary NIS for enhanced network intelligence and service delivery.

2.2 WP2 procedures in action: knowledge sharing

As stated in Section 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3], the NIO facilitates knowledge sharing among NISs deployed within the same or different domains, enabling them to utilize their collective knowledge in deriving execution plans. We exemplify this for two algorithms described in this document: energy-driven virtual RAN (vRAN) orchestration solution (BSvBS), introduced in Section 3.3, and energy-aware VNF placement solution (HADES), introduced in Section 3.1.

2.2.1 Knowledge sharing in the RAN

Figure 2 illustrates a shared representation of two NIFs: BSvBS and HADES. This representation, within the context of the high-level architecture presented in D2.3 [3], highlights the integration of these NIFs and the subsequent identification of additional requirements to enhance the architecture.

Figure 2. Knowledge sharing among two NIFs: BSvBS and HADES.

An important observation is the presence of shared NIF Components (NIF-C) between BSvBS and HADES, indicating the potential for collaborative functionalities. DAEMON's NIP is designed to support such shared components and enables efficient information exchange. For instance, both NIFs rely on energy consumption measurements from an edge cloud platform, which necessitates the sharing of a common source node component.

Furthermore, the depicted figure emphasizes the need for coordination within the architecture, particularly between BSvBS and HADES. BSvBS focuses on generating knowledge about high-performing RAN control policies in relation to the deployed virtualized instances of RAN components. In contrast, HADES is responsible for VNF placement, specifically implementing virtualized RAN functions. This observation underscores the importance of centralized coordination facilitated by the NIP to enable knowledge sharing and foster synergistic performance improvements between the NIFs. By leveraging the NIP's centralized coordination, BSvBS and HADES can effectively share knowledge and mutually benefit from each other's insights.

For example, BSvBS, with its expertise in high-performing RAN control policies, can share its learned knowledge with HADES to improve the placement decisions made by HADES. This shared knowledge allows HADES to optimize VNF placement based on the desired RAN performance objectives set by BSvBS. Conversely, HADES shares its knowledge about energy consumption, latency, and resource availability with BSvBS, enabling BSvBS to refine its RAN control policies and optimize resource allocation.

Through this collaborative knowledge-sharing process, BSvBS and HADES achieve improved performance in terms of energy efficiency, latency reduction, and resource utilization. The integration of their insights and the coordination provided by the NIP enable them to make more informed decisions and enhance the overall architecture's capabilities.

Even though BSvBS and HADES both work in the non-RT-RIC layer, BSvBS produces decisions more often than HADES and needs to share these decisions and other knowledge, e.g., energy, with HADES through the knowledge-sharing procedure shown in Figure 3 as follows:

- After every decision produced by BSvBS, NIO CSOI processes the NISD to check the validity and authenticity of the decision.
- If the decision is valid and authenticated, the NIO CSOI checks against the PolicyIC for the possible conflicts between the decision of BSvBS and the VNF placement of HADES.
- If there is no conflict, NIS CSOI translates the decision of BSvBS to Knowledge rules by requesting knowledge translation of the updated NISD from the Model Explainability block.
- Using updated NISD, PolicyIC block builds the shared knowledge policies, finalizing the centralized knowledge-sharing procedure.

Centralized knowledge sharing among BSvBS and HADES is operated through the Nio-Nifm interface.

Figure 3. NIS Knowledge Sharing process flow [3].

3 Energy-aware VNF orchestration

In this section, we update our work on energy-aware VNF orchestration in a next-generation mobile network. We present the progress in four solutions for virtualized service orchestration at different levels: user/data level placement and autoscaling (Section 3.1 and Section 3.2) and RAN-level VNFs (Section 3.3 and Section 3.4). We report the advancements made on top of the solution descriptions in Section 2 of D4.2 [2].

3.1 Energy-aware VNF placement in Open-Source MANO infrastructures

3.1.1 Solution description

In D4.2 [2], HADES was presented, a solution that supports VNF placement in heterogeneous edge infrastructures by considering the energy consumption as well as the computation and communication delays within a Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI). D4.2 [2] presented the first version of this work with the main components, including the iTAREA module, which provides the optimal deployment of NF in terms of energy and latency. The energy model is based on the estimation of the energy consumption of computation and communication of each NF in the available nodes.

In the present deliverable, a renewed architecture of HADES is presented and proposes a new energy model for the iTAREA module that uses the Gradient Boosted Regression Trees algorithm to forecast the energy consumption.

Figure 4. General overview of (refactored) HADES.

The architecture of the solution has been refactored by explicitly following the network N-Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute over a shared Knowledge (MAPE-K) loop [4]. The refactored solution architecture (shown in Figure 4) defines separated modules for Monitoring (label M in Resource Monitor,) Analyzing (label A in Infrastructure Status Analyzer), Planning (label P in Deployment Configurator and Scheduler) and Executing (label E in Deployment Manager) the placement of VNFs. The knowledge component (label K in VNF/KNF Placement Knowledge) is responsible for maintaining the information retrieved from Kubernetes-based Network Functions (KNF)/VNF repository, the KNF/VNF configuration models, the energy and latency models, storing the monitored infrastructure's status and software and hardware infrastructure characteristics (Central Processing Unit (CPU) power, peripherals, memory, etc.). This modularization supports a better separation of concerns, facilitating the evolution and adaptation of any of the components and the integration of new ones.

In this sense, the infrastructure status analyzer component (label A), which receives monitored data from the resource monitor, incorporates different algorithms to analyze the feasibility of future placements according to the VNF requirements and infrastructure capabilities. With the analysis derived from the results of the algorithms New Devices Finder (NDF) and the Edge-Deployment Alternatives Finder (EDAF) (presented in deliverable (D3.1[4], Section 5.3.3.1), HADES is prepared to foresee if it necessary to scale up the infrastructure (both vertical and horizontal scaling). The NDF algorithm informs about the (new) devices needed to run a specific VNF. Additionally, the evolution of a VNF and/or infrastructure may affect the feasibility of the current VNF's deployment. Some VNFs may require devices with specific

characteristics (in terms of location, configuration, computation capabilities, etc.) that the current infrastructure does not meet. This algorithm detects all VNF's requisites non-supported currently by the infrastructure and returns a minimal configuration (i.e., the minimal set of features and minimal value of the attributes) of the minimal set of nodes needed to deploy the VNF properly, which will be solved by scaling up (vertically or horizontally) the infrastructure. On the other side, the EDAF algorithm informs about the placement decisions that satisfy the requirements of the VNF, including the amount of memory and computing resources required to allocate in each node and the maximal number of users each placement solution would support—allowing to set this last value to return solutions with a minimal number of users supported. This information can be used to scale down (vertically and horizontally) the infrastructure.

Secondly, it allows the introduction of a predictive energy model to be used by the energy-efficient task and resource allocator (iTarea) module, which is part of the Deployment Configurator and Scheduler in Figure 4, uses the energy consumption and latency of the application to optimize the deployment. In D4.2 [2], the energy consumption was estimated using the expression given in Section 3.1.3.1, in D4.1 [1]. This approach provides an accurate energy consumption for nodes with software-limited frequency and for VNFs with communication (in terms of data transmitted and received) known in advance. Now, we propose a new version of the iTarea module that uses a predictive energy model.

Prior to the implementation, we selected a set of techniques that better adapt to the data and the case study at hand. This is because each technique differs from the rest in certain aspects and tends to accommodate the collected data differently. Therefore, whenever training a machine learning model, it is good practice to try different techniques and compare the results obtained. Among the different existing supervised learning techniques, considering the characteristics of the available dataset (from previous experimentation), there are several promising techniques for training. In this case, we have two datasets with few dimensions and few entries (both have 6 dimensions, and none exceeds 1000 entries). Therefore, techniques such as neural networks, which are very sensitive to data scaling, may not perform well on our datasets. Then, we have tested the following techniques:

- **K-Nearest Neighbor Regression:** It is a technique that, despite being simple, often yields quite good results. Its training is fast, and its prediction mechanism is easy to understand. For all these reasons, it is considered a good starting point and a reference for comparative analyses of supervised learning techniques.
- **Linear Regression:** Works such as [5] detail how energy consumption is directly proportional, and even linear, to various resources of a node. Therefore, given that linear regression models attempt to adapt the model to a linear equation, it is quite possible that they will provide good results. In fact, the models studied in GreenOracle [6] are primarily linear models. Hence, linear regression with its potential regularizations can be interesting to study. However, this technique performs better with large datasets that have a high number of features.
- **Regression Trees:** Regression trees are a supervised learning technique known for their speed and not requiring data scaling or preprocessing. Furthermore, Random Forests and Gradient Boosted Regression Trees take it a step further by refining the results obtained by a single tree and mitigating certain shortcomings. The latter techniques may not perform well with datasets that have many features, but that should not be a problem with our datasets [7].
- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** SVM is a powerful supervised learning technique. However, it tends to not perform well with a small number of data points and requires extensive preprocessing. It functions better when its features are interrelated [7].

We applied the same dataset to these regression techniques and, after analyzing and comparing the results and the training and validation error, we found that the Gradient Boosted Regression Trees is the learning technique that best performs best among those studied for our case. Details about the analysis and results will be presented in D5.3.

3.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 1. Energy-aware VNF placement in Open-Source MANO (OSM) usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, NIO gathers the information latency, energy and resource consumption of the infrastructure and the placed VNFs.
Nio-Nifcm	Through this interface, NIO allocates and manages the VIMs of the OSM instance. Also, it is used for gathering information from the OSM Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIM).

Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used to create and instantiate the HADES modules, such as the different iTarea algorithms.
Nifcm-Nivi	Through this interface, the HADES components can be allocated in different locations, preserving energy-awareness.
Nio-MLp	Through this interface, the iTarea module that uses a predictive energy model can access the ML model training features.
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (this solution does not require such integration by now).
Nio-Mano	Through this interface, NIO can decide on different iTarea algorithms depending on the current energy consumption, available resources and infrastructure and Network Orchestrator (NO) status.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with the Open MANO OSM.

3.1.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

This solution leverages the NIF management and the knowledge-sharing procedures discussed in Sections 5.1.3 and 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3]. The infrastructure status analyzer algorithm monitors the VIMs and VNF/KNFs through the knowledge-sharing procedure. As a result, the analysis is used by the deployment configurator and the iTarea algorithm with the aim of producing the optimal energy-aware placement.

3.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 2. Energy-aware VNF placement in OSM infrastructures. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [2]	Status	Discussion
FR-EAWVNF-000	Successful (95%)	Hades can estimate the energy consumption of VNFs both in simulated and real environments, obtaining possibly similar results. The energy model is described in D4.2 [2] and updated in this deliverable.
FR-EAWVNF-001	Successful (100%)	In the placement solution presented in D4.2 [2], the energy model used to estimate energy consumption includes both CPU and data transmission.
FR-EAWVNF-001.00	Successful (100%)	In the placement solution presented in D4.2 [2], the energy model used to estimate energy consumption explicitly includes the energy cost of computation calculated from the CPU cycles and the CPU frequency, along with other factors.
FR-EAWVNF-001.01	Successful (100%)	In HADES presented in D4.2 [2], the energy model explicitly includes the energy cost of data communication calculated in the amount of bytes sent and received along with other terms.
FR-EAWVNF-002	Successful (100%)	HADES, presented in D4.2 [2], monitors the impact of hardware resources of VNFs in the estimation of energy consumption. The solution also considers the computation, communication, and storage resources as part of the placement algorithm.
FR-EAWVNF-004.00	Successful (100%)	iTarea decision in D4.2 [2] has the specificity of an energy profile considering requirements that are related to the execution location context, such as the available Random Access Memory (RAM), storage, or specific hardware/server configurations. Based on the different constraints above, the solution allows selecting the nodes where VNFs can be run to reduce energy consumption while meeting the needs of the infrastructure.
FR-EAWVNF-004.01	Successful (100%)	iTarea (both in D4.2 [2] and this deliverable) considers the energy cost of computing VNF placement, which is considered part of the global energy footprint of the solution. The placement decision considers the computational and communication energy consumption of VNFs based on their location in the infrastructure to place them in an energy-efficient manner.
NFR-EAWVNF-002	Partial (60%)	The energy-aware placement solution reduces up to 51% of the energy consumption compared with the default deployment proposed by the existing MANO standard solutions, which follow non-energy-aware policies.
NFR-EAWVNF-001	Successful (100%)	The energy-aware placement solution scales well when considering a heterogenous set of devices and network infrastructure in simulated environments.

3.2 A proactive auto-scaling solution for energy-aware VNF placement in edge-based infrastructures

3.2.1 Solution description

We refer the reader to Section 2.2 of D4.2 [2] for a complete description of the solution.

3.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 3. Proactive autoscaling solution for energy-aware VNF placement usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, NIO gathers information on failed requests of the solution and monitors the state of the solution.
Nio-Nifcm	Through this interface, NIO can restrict the algorithm in the solution to choose the scaling and placing decisions from a given subset of essential nodes by considering the resource limitations.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used to create and instantiate the workload predictor, the Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) module and the energy-aware orchestrator and share the scaling and placement decisions of the algorithms with the NIF manager.
Nifcm-Nivi	Through this interface, the energy-aware orchestrator and the proactive auto-scaling module algorithms can share the scaling and placement decisions by taking into consideration the computation resources and the status of the worker nodes.
Nio-MLp	The selector algorithm of the context-aware predictor framework uses this interface for selecting the ML model that better fits the current workload pattern identified by the Context Analyzer.
Mlo-Ncat	Through this interface, the Context Analyzer, in the context-aware predictor framework, identifies the execution context of the NF (i.e., decreasing, increasing, and fluctuating workload).
Nio-Mano	Through this interface, NIO can decide on different operation modes of the ENI module depending on the current status of the resources.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with the EdgeCloudSim simulator [8] to execute the scaling and placement decisions produced by the solution.

3.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

This solution leverages the knowledge-sharing procedures discussed in Section 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3]. The context-aware predictor framework and the Essential node identifier module use the information of the infrastructure status through the knowledge-sharing procedure. By using these predictions and status, the two algorithms in this solution produce the optimal scaling and placement decisions to manage the NIF.

3.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 4. Proactive auto-scaling solution for energy-aware VNF placement in edge-based infrastructures. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [2]	Status	Discussion
FR-EAWVNF-000	Successful (95%)	The energy-aware solution presented in D4.2 [2] estimates the energy consumption of VNF for the EdgeCloudSim simulator [8].
FR-EAWVNF-001.00	Successful (100%)	In the placement and autoscaling solution presented in D4.2 [2], the energy consumption model calculates the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of CPU usage according to the edge/cloud node in which VNFs are going to be deployed.
FR-EAWVNF-001.01	Successful (100%)	In the autoscaling and placement solution in D4.2 [2], the energy consumption model calculates the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of the amount of data transmitted (sent and received) according to the edge/cloud node in which VNFs are deployed.
FR-EAWVNF-003.00	Successful (100%)	The energy consumption model used in the proactive autoscaling solution and VNF placement presented in D4.2 [2] can be used to calculate the energy footprint of VNF migration due to virtualization costs and data transmission cost as (horizontal) virtualization scaling energy cost is considered in this solution.

FR-EAWVNF-003.01	Successful (100%)	The energy consumption model used in the proactive autoscaling solution and VNF placement presented in D4.2 [2] can be used to calculate the energy footprint of VNF migration due to data transmission costs as data transmission cost is considered in this solution and can be used to calculate transfer cost in terms of data sent and received.
FR-EAWVNF-006.00	Partial (25%)	In D4.2 [2], the proactive autoscaling solution and VNF placement consider the energy consumption of horizontal scaling explicitly to optimize VNF placement. As vertical scaling is more complex, it is under consideration how to extend the proactive energy consumption model presented in D4.2 [2] to calculate the energy footprint of VNFs' vertical scaling, but it is in a preliminary stage.
FR-EAWVNF-006.01	Successful (100%)	The proactive autoscaling solution and VNF placement presented in D4.2 [2] explicitly consider the energy consumption of horizontal scaling to optimize VNF placement. This solution considers both the base (idle) and dynamic (due to service execution) energy consumption of the nodes, as well as the energy consumption of node scaling.
NFR-EAWVNF-002	Partial (60%)	The proactive autoscaling solution and VNF placement presented in D4.2 [2] have a 92.5% decrease in energy consumption (a failed request rate of up to 0% and reasonable execution times of the auto-scaling process for different problem sizes).
FR-EAWVNF-004.00	Successful (100%)	The proactive auto-scaling solution and VNF placement presented in D4.2 [2] explicitly include a module for energy-aware orchestration. This energy-aware orchestrator calculates the energy consumption according to the location of the VNFs and assigns the applications/VNFs to the most energy-efficient node.
NFR-EAWVNF-004	Successful (100%)	The energy-aware orchestrator, as well as the ENI module presented in D4.2 [2], includes the expected performance as a constraint to reduce energy consumption without compromising throughput.
NFR-EAWVNF-001	Successful (100%)	The energy-aware placement solution scales well when considering a heterogeneous set of devices and network infrastructure in a simulated environment.

3.3 Energy-driven vRAN orchestration

3.3.1 Solution description

A problem of energy-driven vRAN orchestration was defined in Section 3.2 of D4.1 [1], and an RL-based solution that works in the Non-RT-RIC timescale was introduced in Section 2.3 of D4.2 [2]. In this section, we introduce two (2) more solutions, which both work in the non-RT Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC), as shown in Figure 5. In section 3.3.1.1, we provide a solution based on bandit scheduling, and in Section 3.3.1.2, we provide a solution based on loss meta-learning.

Figure 5. Integration of energy-driven vRAN orchestration solutions in O-RAN architecture.

3.3.1.1 *Solution based on bandit scheduling*

This work [9] aims to propose and evaluate a robust algorithm that identifies efficient meta-policies in the non-RT-RIC of O-RAN architecture and is oblivious to the underlying virtual Base Station (vBS) operation, their hosting platforms, network conditions, and data traffic (or, user demands). More specifically, our system establishes thresholds for the important vBS operating controls, including the vBS transmission power, the permissible Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), and the duty cycle (or airtime) in both the downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) directions. The real-time schedulers that fine-tune the vBS settings get the policy's updates at a scale that is close to real-time.

The fundamental concept is to formulate the vBS scheduling as a bandit learning issue and create an algorithm whose performance is provably optimum under a wide range of constraints. The combined aim of effective throughput (i.e., modified by user traffic) and energy consumption, where the latter can be prioritized via a tunable weight value, is the optimality criteria we apply. Additionally, unlike other research, our approach is lightweight and has low overheads, making it simple to put into practice.

Model. We consider time-slotted system operation in alignment with O-RAN specs, where each slot represents a period (range of a few seconds) over which a certain policy is being applied. We optimize the system operation over a time horizon of $t = 1, \dots, T$ slots. Our policy includes thresholds for specific scheduling controls that are key to vBS performance. In detail, for the DL operation, we define the set of maximum allowed vBS transmission power control (TPC) $P_d = \{p_i^d, \forall i \in [H]\}$, the set of highest eligible MCS $M_d = \{m_i^d, \forall i \in [I]\}$ and the set of maximum vBS transmission airtime or duty cycle $A_d = \{a_i^d, \forall i \in [J]\}$ where H, I and J denote the number of transmission power, MCS, and airtime levels in DL, respectively. Hence, in period t , we determine the DL control $x_t^d \in P_d \times M_d \times A_d$.

For the UL operation, we introduce the set $M_u = \{m_i^u, \forall i \in [K]\}$ and $A_u = \{a_i^u, \forall i \in [L]\}$, where K and L express the number of MCS and airtime levels in UL, respectively. Thus, the UL control in period t is $x_t^u \in M_u \times A_u$. Following the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) specs, we assume these controls take values from a finite set that includes all possible combinations $X \in P_d \times M_d \times A_d \times M_u \times A_u$, and thus, the radio policy in period t is specified as $x_t = (x_t^d, x_t^u) \in X$.

The performance criterion is to maximize the reward function $f_t(x_t) = U_t(x_t) - \delta P_t(x_t)$, where $P_t(\cdot)$ is a black-box function measuring either the total power consumption of the vBS or the CPU consumption of the Base Band Unit (BBU) and $U_t(\cdot)$ is the following utility function $U_t(x_t) = \log\left(1 + \frac{R_t^d(x_t^d)}{d_t^d}\right) + \log\left(1 + \frac{R_t^u(x_t^u)}{d_t^u}\right)$. We note that d_t^d and d_t^u refer to the user demands in DL and UL, respectively, at slot t , and R_t^d, R_t^u concern the data transmitted during the same slot.

It is crucial to note that both reward components vary with time. There are several factors contributing to this effect. First, the user traffic that shapes U_t changes, sometimes drastically, e.g., in small cell networks where user churn is high. Second, the network conditions might as well vary (in slow, fast, or mixed timescales), and this affects the achieved data transmissions (hence U_t changes even for fixed x_t) but also impacts the energy cost P_t (low Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) induces more BBU processing costs). Third, the operation cost of the vBS hosting platform is subject to variations of external computing loads (e.g., when co-hosting other services or other vBS), changes in the monetary cost (or availability) of the energy price, and so on. Importantly, all the above factors are unknown at the beginning of each scheduling period t . Indeed, it is challenging to predict the user loads, energy availability, channel conditions, etc., over a few seconds. This, in turn, means that often, in practice, when we decide x_t in each slot, we do not have access to the function f_t .

Achievable regret. The goal of our algorithm is to find a sequence of configurations $\{x_t\}_{t=1}^T$ that aggregate rewards so as to approach, asymptotically, the cumulative reward achieved by the single best configuration. Formally, we employ the metric of static expected regret:

$$R_T = \max_{x \in X} \{\sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x)\} - E[\sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_t)],$$

where the first term describes the best configuration that can be only selected with hindsight, i.e., with a priori knowledge of all future reward functions until T ; and the second term measures the achieved cumulative reward by our policy. Note that the expectation is induced by any possible randomization in the selection of $\{x_t\}$ that is introduced by our learner. Eventually, our objective is to devise a rule that decides the configurations in such a way that the average regret, for any possible realization of rewards $\{f_t\}_{t=1}^T$, diminishes asymptotically to zero, i.e., $\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_T}{T} = 0$.

The details of the proposed algorithm, called BSvBS, can be found in Figure 6.

Algorithm 1: Bandit Scheduling for vBS (BSvBS)

```

1 Input: Horizon  $T$ ; Configurations  $|\mathcal{X}|$ ;
2 Initialize:  $\gamma = \min \left\{ 1, \sqrt{\frac{|\mathcal{X}| \ln |\mathcal{X}|}{(e-1)T}} \right\}$ ;
    $w_1(x) \leftarrow 1, \forall x \in \mathcal{X}$ .
3 for  $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$  do
4   Update the distribution using (5).
5   Sample next configuration:  $x_t \sim y_t$ .
6   Receive & scale reward  $f_t(x_t)$ .
7   Calculate weighted feedback using (7).
8   Update the weights using (6).
end

```

Figure 6. Pseudocode of the proposed algorithm BSvBS.

Where equations (5), (6) and (7) in Figure 6 refer to $y_t(x) = \frac{\gamma}{|\mathcal{X}|} + \frac{(1-\gamma)w_t(x)}{\sum_{x' \in \mathcal{X}} w_t(x')}$, $w_{t+1}(x) = w_t(x) \exp\left(\gamma \frac{\Phi_t(x)}{|\mathcal{X}|}\right)$, and $\Phi_t(x) = \frac{f_t(x_t)}{y_t(x_t)}$ if $x = x_t$ and 0 otherwise, respectively.

Lemma. Let $T > 0$ be a fixed time horizon. Set input parameter $\gamma = \min \left\{ 1, \sqrt{\frac{|\mathcal{X}| \ln |\mathcal{X}|}{(e-1)T}} \right\}$. Then, running BSvBS ensures that the expected regret is:

$$R_T \leq 2\sqrt{e-1} \sqrt{T|\mathcal{X}| \ln |\mathcal{X}|}.$$

3.3.1.2 Solution based on loss meta-learning

Loss meta-learning is a different but equally viable approach to address the problem of energy-driven vRAN orchestration. This strategy is outlined in its most up-to-date version in Section 7.1.3 of D2.3 [3], and described in full in [10]. Specifically, loss meta-learning can support automated decision-making in a vRAN management scenario where the operator must decide on the functional split of the Physical layer/Medium Access Control (PHY/MAC) function pipeline between Distributed Units (DU) residing closer to the radio access, and more powerful Central Units (CU) towards the Edge [11]. Consistently with the energy-driven nature of the task, the primary goal of the operator is ensuring the RAN sustainability, by maximizing its energy efficiency [12].

Let us assume a specific scenario where N DUs handle the aggregated traffic generated from a set of Remote Units (RU) each. The DUs are associated with a single CU through high-speed mid-haul connectivity. Processing each PHY/MAC function has a different energy cost at the DUs and CU. The energy consumption at each DU is directly proportional to the traffic volume that it has to handle at a given time since the equipment must always be active. Conversely, the CU runs a number of physical machines (PMs) that can be dynamically turned on/off based on the incoming demand by the DUs [12]. All PMs are identical and thus have the same energy model [13]: activating a new PM incurs a start-up cost, then the energy consumption increases proportionally to the computing load of the PM. Note that we assume that the increment of energy per traffic unit is lower at PMs than at DUs, as the CU features more expensive and scalable equipment.

Given the traffic demand at one DU, different functional splits entail diverse computational loads at the DU and CU as they move PHY/MAC functions from the former to the latter. The MANO objective is then deciding, for each DU and decision time, what functional split shall be used to minimize the total energy cost of the vRAN system. It is important to stress that since this is a preemptive decision, it must be based on a forecast of the mobile data traffic that the DU will observe during the next decision interval.

Once those decisions are taken, the CU will only activate the minimum required number of PMs to serve the total incoming demand from all DUs. For that, at the start of each decision time, the CU receives the estimated traffic and functional split per DU and applies a near-optimal bin-packing heuristic to calculate the minimum number of PMs required and the associated assignment of PMs to DUs.

We remark that, in practice, the network operator does not know the policy on PM activation decided by the cloud provider hosting the CU or the exact power consumption behavior of the PMs and DUs equipment. Still, the operator must take functional split decisions and reserve compute capacity in the CU without such information. In addition, the fact that the PM activation decision depends on all DUs sets the stage for a clear instance of intertwined predictions under unknown objectives – which is precisely where loss meta-learning comes in handy, as explained in Section 7.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

Figure 7. Implementation of the loss meta-learning approach in the vRAN management architecture.

As a matter of fact, the most recent loss meta-learning approach developed by the DAEMON project allows the implementation of a data-driven network function that jointly takes care of both (i) deciding on the functional split at each DU and (ii) forecasting the traffic at each DU used to request computing capacity at the CU. We can see in Figure 7 how the detailed model for loss meta-learning is integrated into the control plane as a so-called “AutoManager” component. In this case, the input to the AutoManager block is composed of N different traffic flows, one for each one of the DUs. The loss meta-learning-powered AutoManager receives the past samples of these flows, and it outputs two sets of values: the first set is a variable per DU that states the specific functional split that is selected, and the second set contains the amount of processing from each DU required at the CU as result of the selected functional split and predicted load. This decision is then implemented and the energy consumption is measured a-posteriori so that it can be fed back to AutoManager to train the algorithm and learn the appropriate loss function.

3.3.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.3.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 5. Energy-driven vRAN orchestration usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, NIO gathers information on the scheduling utility function of the solution and monitors the state of the solution.
Nio-Nifcm	Through this interface, NIO can modify the precision of the configuration set, considering the resource limitations.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used to share the meta-scheduling decisions of the algorithm with the NIF manager.
Nifcm-Nivi	Through this interface, BSvBS algorithm shares the a-scheduling decisions.
Nio-MLp	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Nio-Mano	Through this interface, NIO can use different schedulers with this solution as the meta-scheduler.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with other O-RAN components to employ the scheduling decisions produced by the solution.

3.3.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management and the knowledge-sharing procedures discussed in Sections 5.1.3 and 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3]. BSvBS algorithm monitors the schedulers through the knowledge-sharing procedure. As a result, the algorithm in this solution produces the optimal meta-scheduling decisions to manage the NIF.

3.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 6. Energy-driven vRAN orchestration. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-EAWVNF-000	Successful (100%)	As described in the solution description, this NI Functionality monitors the power consumption profile of O-RAN base stations.
FR-EAWVNF-005	Successful (100%)	As described in the solution description, this NI Functionality uses the power consumption profile of O-RAN base stations to make decisions on configuring the vBS.
NFR-EAWVNF-004	Successful (100%)	The BSvBS algorithm aims at balancing network throughput and energy consumption in vRANs.

3.4 Energy-driven joint vRAN & edge service orchestration

3.4.1 Solution description

In D4.1 [1], Section 3.3, we presented a problem where RAN resources and edge services are jointly optimized to attain a target level of service performance while minimizing the edge energy consumption.

Figure 8: O-RAN compliant system architecture.

Recapping, we consider a GPU-powered edge server providing an AI service through a RAN. Specifically, we consider an object recognition service that can be used, for instance, for security surveillance or fault detection in industrial chains. We assume a slice dedicated to this service is created including vBS and the edge server. The workflow is very simple: users capture images that are sent to the edge server through the UL channel of the radio interface of the vBS. Then, the edge server’s GPU processes the incoming data and generates a response, which is sent back to the users via the DL channel of the vBS.

We consider a Learning Agent (LA) that oversees controlling the GPU, the resources assigned to the network slice, and the amount of data sent by the user via a set of *control policies*. We follow closely the framework of O-RAN. That is, the LA runs in the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) in the timescale of seconds. Because our LA provides both radio and edge computing control policies, it interacts with the NRT RIC and the edge orchestrator therein. Radio policies are, in turn, enforced by the NRT RIC by using O-RAN’s E2 interface. Figure 8 summarizes the architecture of the system. Feedback from the data plane components is collected by the Edge orchestrator and NRT RIC (via O-RAN’s O1 interface) and then fed to the LA. This allows us to use RL to solve our problem.

Namely, we formulate the problem as a contextual multi-armed bandit or *contextual bandit*. Further details concerning the formal definition of the context space, action space, and reward were introduced in D4.1 [1], Section 3.3.

The energy consumption of each entity, namely the vBS and the server (including components such as the Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) model and motherboard), can significantly vary due to their form factors and configurations. Moreover, the value or scarcity of energy can fluctuate based on the situation. For instance, energy is a precious commodity for a Power over Ethernet (PoE) or a solar-powered vBS. The energy’s value at the edge can also change from day to night based on the rates determined by power suppliers in different countries.

To encompass these diverse scenarios, we introduced the following *cost function*:

$$u(c, x) = \delta_1 p^s(c, x) + \delta_2 p^b(c, x)$$

where δ_1 and δ_2 signify the costs of power at the edge server and the vBS, each measured in monetary units per watt (mu/W).

In our study, we focus on service-level performance constraints, surpassing other studies that only look at lower-level performance requirements like data rate or delay. The relationship between context-action pairs and service-level performance indicators is intricate, and currently, there are no existing models to map this, which we elaborate on in D4.1's [1] experimental results (see Section 3.3). Hence, we resort to observational learning. For our object recognition service, we have two constraints: (i) a maximum service delay, d^{max} , directly tied to the user's frame rate, and (ii) a minimum mAP, ρ^{min} , representing the accuracy baseline of the service in object detection. We then formulated the problem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\{x_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}}{\text{minimize}} && \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T u(c_t, x_t) \\ & \text{subject to} && d_t(c_t, x_t) \leq d^{max}, \quad \forall t = 1, 2, \dots \\ & && \rho_t(c_t, x_t) \geq \rho^{min}, \quad \forall t = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

The problem's nature requires a contextual bandit formulation, meaning we have to choose a control policy x_t for every time period t , given the context c_t . The optimal decision at each t relies solely on the current context c_t , and the performance indicators are observed at the end of each period. Our goal is long-term cost minimization while meeting the constraint at each time period.

Practical considerations and detailed decisions that we took in the design of our solution, which we name EdgeBOL, can be found in [14]. In the following, we simply present a summary. EdgeBOL is an online learning algorithm that solves the contextual bandit problem defined above. Most of the existing contextual bandit algorithms assume a linear relationship between the contexts-control space and the associated or a certain reward function structure. However, as the measurements in D4.1 [1], Section 3.3, revealed, our performance metrics have a non-linear and almost arbitrary structure, though with a high correlation with our control policies. That is, a small change in one of the policies (e.g., image resolution) will produce a small change in the service delay and the consumed power. This allows us to get information about unobserved context-control points by observing nearby points, hence reducing the exploration time.

Based on these observations, we propose a Bayesian online learning method that models the cost and constraints as samples of Gaussian Processes (GPs) over the joint context-control space. This non-parametric estimator deals with the aforementioned non-linearities and correlations and quantifies the function estimation uncertainty, effectively addressing the exploration vs. exploitation trade-off.

Function approximator. In order to estimate the cost and constraint functions, we use GPs, which consist of a collection of random variables that follow joint Gaussian distributions. Let $z \in \mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{X}$ denote a context-control pair. We model each of the unknown functions as a sample from $GP(\mu(z), k(z, z'))$, where $\mu(z)$ is its mean function and $k(z, z')$ denotes its kernel or covariance function. We assume $\mu = 0$ and $k(z, z') < 1$, which we refer to as the *prior distribution*, not conditioned on data. Given the prior distribution and a set of observations, the *posterior distribution* can be computed using closed-form formulas.

The sets of observations of the cost and constraint functions at points $Z_T = [z_1, \dots, z_T]$ up to time period T are denoted by $y_T^{(0)} = [u_1, \dots, u_T]$, $y_T^{(1)} = [d_1, \dots, d_T]$, $y_T^{(2)} = [\rho_1, \dots, \rho_T]$, respectively, assuming i.i.d. Gaussian noise $\sim N(0, \zeta_{(i)}^2)$. The posterior distribution of these functions follows a GP distribution with mean $\mu_T^{(i)}(z)$ and covariance $k_T^{(i)}(z, z')$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_T^{(i)}(z) &= k_T^{(i)}(z)^\top (K_T^{(i)} + \zeta_{(i)}^2 I_T)^{-1} y_T^{(i)} \\ k_T^{(i)}(z, z') &= k^{(i)}(z, z') - k_T^{(i)}(z)^\top (K_T^{(i)} + \zeta_{(i)}^2 I_T)^{-1} k_T^{(i)}(z') \end{aligned}$$

where $k_T^{(i)}(z) = [k^{(i)}(z_1, z), \dots, k^{(i)}(z_T, z)]^\top$, $K_T^{(i)}(z)$ is a kernel matrix defined as $[k^{(i)}(z, z')]_{z, z' \in Z_T}$, I_T is the T -dimension identity matrix, and $\zeta_{(i)}^2$ the variance of noise in observations. Index i denotes the objective function, with $i = 0$ for the cost function, $i = 1$ for the delay, and $i = 2$ for the mAP. The distribution of unobserved values of $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ for function i is computed from the prior distribution, vector Z_T and the observed values $y_T^{(i)}$ using both previous equations.

Kernel selection. The kernel function shapes the GP's prior and posterior distributions and, hence, has an impact on the algorithm's performance. It encodes the correlation of the function values for every pair of context-control points. That is, the kernel characterizes the *smoothness* of the functions. The properties of the kernel function should be thoroughly selected for each specific application and the underlying functions have to be learned. Thus, we use the experimental data analyzed in D4.1 [1], Section 3.3, to

conclude that the kernel function should satisfy two properties for all the functions: *stationarity* and *anisotropy*. This means that the kernel $k(z, z')$ is invariant to translations in \mathcal{Z} but not invariant to rotations in \mathcal{Z} . The smoothness of the kernel for each dimension of function i is encoded in the length-scale vector $\mathcal{L}^{(i)} = [l_1^{(i)}, \dots, l_N^{(i)}]$, where N indicates the number of dimensions of \mathcal{Z} . The distance between two points based on the length-scale vector is given by

$$d^{(i)}(z, z') = \sqrt{(z - z')^\top (L^{(i)})^{-2} (z - z')},$$

where $L^{(i)} = \text{diag}(\mathcal{L}^{(i)})$ is a diagonal matrix of the length-scale vector. In order to satisfy the properties stated above, we select the Matérn kernel on its anisotropic version. Moreover, following standard practice, we particularize it with parameter $\nu = \frac{3}{2}$, indicating that the function is at least once differentiable. Thus, the expression of the kernel can be particularized as follows:

$$k^{(i)}(z, z') = (1 + \sqrt{3}d^{(i)}(z, z')) \exp(-\sqrt{3}d^{(i)}(z, z')).$$

Note that although we are using the same kernel for all the functions (cost and constraints), their hyperparameters will vary depending on their shape. In fact, the hyperparameters $\mathcal{L}^{(i)}$ and noise variance $\zeta_{(i)}^2$ should be optimized for each function i before running the algorithm by maximizing the likelihood estimation over prior data. During execution, the hyperparameters shall remain constant; if the hyperparameters are optimized with newly acquired data, it is not guaranteed that the GP's confidence interval will cover the true function within, causing the optimization to fall into poor local optima.

Safe set. It is crucial to identify first which controls satisfy the constraints, which, however, depends also on the context. For instance, when the user's channel quality decreases (the context changes), the user uses a lower MCS, which increases the transmission time, hence increasing the service delay. Therefore, the controls that are suitable for high channel quality may not meet the delay constraint with low channel quality. We define the *safe set* as the set of policies that satisfy all the constraints for a given context c :

$$S(c) = \{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid d(c, x) \leq d^{\max} \wedge \rho(x) \geq \rho^{\min}\}$$

Nevertheless, the computation of the safe set is very challenging for several reasons. Firstly, the observations of the performance indicators are noisy due to the stochastic nature of the system, as we observed in the empirical analysis reported in D4.1 [1], Section 3.3. Secondly, the number of available controls $|\mathcal{X}|$ is usually very large in practice, making it unfeasible to explore all controls for all possible contexts. For that reason, we use the GPs to compute an estimation of the safe set:

$$S_t = \{ x \in \mathcal{X} \mid \mu_{t-1}^{(1)}(c_t, x) + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^{(1)}(c_t, x) \leq d^{\max} \\ \wedge \mu_{t-1}^{(2)}(c_t, x) - \beta \sigma_{t-1}^{(2)}(c_t, x) \geq \rho^{\min} \}$$

where $(\sigma_t^{(i)}(z))^2 = k_t^{(i)}(z, z)$ and β is a weighting parameter. Note that at each time period t the point z_t is observed and the vectors Z_t and $y_t^{(i)} \forall i$ are updated consequently. Due to their correlation, the posterior distribution of points near z_t will vary, having an impact on the controls that will be included in the safe set in $t + 1$.

Acquisition function. It indicates, at each time period t , which control x_t shall be used in the system given context c_t . This task is crucial for the convergence of the algorithm and needs to interleave an exploration process in order to expand the safe set while seeking a safe control with high performance. Many previous works have proposed acquisition functions for constrained Bayesian optimization, but they do not consider contexts. We use the contextual Lower Confidence Bound (LCB) as an acquisition function, but *constrained to the safe set*:

$$x_t = \underset{x \in S_t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mu_{t-1}^{(0)}(c_t, x) - \sqrt{\beta} \sigma_{t-1}^{(0)}(c_t, x).$$

The algorithm shown in Figure 9 summarizes the whole workflow EdgeBOL. At the beginning of the time period t , the context c_t is observed (line 4). Based on the observed context c_t and the vectors Z_{t-1} and $y_{t-1}^{(i)} \forall i$ from the previous time period, the posterior distribution of all the functions is computed using eq. - (line 5). Note that when we do not have observations ($Z_0 = \emptyset, y_0^{(i)} = \emptyset, \forall i$) the posterior distribution is equal to the prior distribution. Using the expectation and uncertainty of the constraint functions and the equations presented before, the safe set S_t is built (line 6). The control x_t is selected from the safe set S_t based on the posterior distribution of the cost function and the acquisition function (line 7). At the end of the time period t , all the performance indicators are observed. Then, the cost function is computed. Finally, the new context-control pair z_t , the value of the cost function $u_t(c_t, x_t)$ and the value of the constraint functions ($d_t(c_t, x_t)$ and $p_t(c_t, x_t)$) are added to their respective vectors to generate Z_t and $y_t^{(i)} \forall i$ (lines 10-13). The source code of EdgeBOL is publicly available online¹.

¹ https://github.com/jaayala/constrained_bayes_opt

Algorithm 1 EdgeBOL

```

1: Inputs: Control Space  $\mathcal{X}$ , kernel  $k$ ,  $S_0$ ,  $\beta$ ,  $\delta_1$ ,  $\delta_2$ ,  $\rho^{min}$ ,  $d^{max}$ 
2: Initialize:  $Z_0 = \emptyset$ ,  $y_0^{(i)} = \emptyset$ ,  $\forall i$ .
3: for  $t = 1, 2, \dots$  do
4:   Observe the context  $c_t$ 
5:   Compute  $\mu_{t-1}^{(i)}$ ,  $\sigma_{t-1}^{(i)} \forall i$ 
6:   Estimate the safe set:  $S_t = S_0 \cup \{x \in \mathcal{X} | \mu_{t-1}^{(1)}(c_t, x) + \beta\sigma_{t-1}^{(1)}(c_t, x) \leq d^{max} \wedge \mu_{t-1}^{(2)}(c_t, x) - \beta\sigma_{t-1}^{(2)}(c_t, x) \geq \rho^{min}\}$ 
7:    $x_t = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in S_t} \mu_{t-1}^{(0)}(c_t, x) - \sqrt{\beta_t} \sigma_{t-1}^{(0)}(c_t, x)$ 
8:   Observe  $d_t(c_t, x_t)$ ,  $\rho_t(c_t, x_t)$ ,  $p_t^s(c_t, x_t)$ , and  $p_t^b(c_t, x_t)$  at the end of the time period  $t$ 
9:   Compute the cost  $u_t(c_t, x_t) = \delta_1 p_t^s(c, x) + \delta_2 p_t^b(c, x)$ 
10:  Update  $Z_t \leftarrow Z_{t-1} \cup [c_t, x_t]$ 
11:  Update  $y_t^{(0)} \leftarrow y_{t-1}^{(0)} \cup u_t(c_t, x_t)$ 
12:  Update  $y_t^{(1)} \leftarrow y_{t-1}^{(1)} \cup d_t(c_t, x_t)$ 
13:  Update  $y_t^{(2)} \leftarrow y_{t-1}^{(2)} \cup \rho_t(c_t, x_t)$ 
14: end for

```

Figure 9. EdgeBOL algorithm.

An empirical performance evaluation of EdgeBOL will be presented in D5.3.

3.4.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.4.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 7. EdgeBOL usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	EdgeBOL reports statistics related to the operation of the intelligent components through this interface. As we discussed above, all the metrics related to explainability are reported back to the Nio, through this interface, and the conflict resolution policy is inserted.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to assign computing resources to the EdgeBOL agent and place the corresponding xApp in the domain of the O-RAN Non-RT RIC.
Nifm-Nifnis	Besides the standard creation and termination procedures, this interface is used to configure some parameters in EdgeBOL, such as the KPI constraints of the service under EdgeBOL control.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used to allocate enough computing resources required by the Bayesian Learning agent in EdgeBOL.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to issue possible re-training of the system due to changing conditions, e.g., new KPI constraints that need to be met by EdgeBOL.
Mlo-Ncat	The created models are pushed into the catalog through this interface.
Nio-Mano	Through this interface, the NIO can issue re-orchestration requests to the vRAN/edge system when inference is severely delayed due to a deficit of computing capacity.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with O-RAN components relevant to EdgeBOL: SMO and Non-RT RIC.

3.4.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated when the service KPI constraints are frequently violated. In this case, the NIO can either relax the KPI or use the Nio-Ext interface to request O-RAN SMO for more computing resources.
2. In either case, the NIO looks into the NIS catalog for a trained model with the new scenario. If none exist, a re-training process is triggered.
3. Models are validated and submitted to the O-Cloud, through the Nio-Ext and Nifm-Nifnis interfaces.
4. The O-Cloud system Acknowledges the new parameters.

3.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 8. Energy-driven joint vRAN & edge service orchestration. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-EAWVNF-000	Successful (100%)	EdgeBOL learns the energy footprint of a virtualized base station and a service deployed at the edge to minimize energy consumption subject to meeting certain service KPIs.
FR-EAWVNF-005	Successful (100%)	EdgeBOL is designed to exploit O-RAN's interfaces to configure virtualized radio access networks to minimize energy consumption subject to meeting certain service KPIs.
NFR-EAWVNF-006	Successful (100%)	The solution described in this section is specifically designed to meet service-specific KPIs such as image classification performance while minimizing energy consumption.

4 Capacity forecasting

In this section, we provide an update on our progress in capacity forecasting for anticipatory networking. We present the improvements built upon the developments in D4.2 [2] in the following four use cases, including resource allocation, VM reservation, cost reduction for video streaming, and prediction-assisted network scheduling.

4.1 Anticipatory capacity allocation with admission control

In Section 3.1 of Deliverable 4.2 of the project [2], we introduced a capacity forecasting use-case that targets a scenario where anticipatory NI is in charge of capacity allocation to slices. In the third project iteration, we extended this use case by considering the joint problem of slice admission control (AC) and resource reservation (RR). While RR maps to the capacity allocation tackled in the previous iteration, AC is a new component of the use case. Specifically, we study the joint AC/RR problem while considering new opportunities for operators to optimize their revenues. To this end, we adopt an approach of slice overbooking during AC. Slice overbooking takes advantage of slice demand multiplexing to reduce resource utilization while maximizing the QoE of end users [15].

4.1.1 Solution description

We propose two different approaches for an NI that automates the decision process of AC/RR under slice overbooking. The first relies on a hybrid model that – similarly to the previous approach for anticipatory capacity allocation introduced in the previous iteration of the project – brings together deep learning and a traditional tool like optimization; the model is formally introduced in Section 7.2.9 of Deliverable 2.3 of the project [3]; the second approach is instead based on the enhanced loss meta-learning models presented in Section 7.1.3 of that same deliverable. The two solutions are not directly competing; rather, they apply to different scenarios: the former can be applied when full system knowledge is available a priori, while the latter is suitable when the target performance is not fully known at design time. Next, we introduce the two different solutions. Details can be found in the associated publications [10], [16].

4.1.1.1 *Solution based on hybrid machine learning and optimization*

Our solution is named kaNSaaS for overbooking-aware Network Slicing as a Service and follows the high-level concept outlined in Figure 35 of D2.3 [3] of the project. Specifically, our design stems from the consideration that both AC and RR are inherently anticipatory decisions in nature but operate at different timescales. On the one hand, in AC, the mobile network operator (MNO) must admit slices at the start of each Service Level Agreement (SLA) block so as to ensure that their demand is accommodated during the future T_{SLA} time interval, i.e., the period during which a constant capacity is requested by the service provider (SP). On the other hand, in Resource Allocation (RA), the MNO has to reserve resources at the beginning of each T_{RA} , i.e., the RA block interval during which the capacity allocated by the MNO to a slice remains constant, in a way to best serve the traffic through the following T_{RA} interval. As illustrated in Figure 35 of D2.3 [3], $T_{\text{SLA}} > T_{\text{RA}}$, as the MNO can perform a faster and more accurate anticipatory allocation of resources than what asked over longer timescales by the SP.

Our design abides by the observations above and hinges upon tailored forecasting models that support decision-making at two different timescales, namely long-term SLA blocks and short-term RA blocks.

- First, at every T_{SLA} time slot, the MNO computes slice demand predictions that inform a tentative resource allocation for the next T_{SLA} time interval. In turn, this provisional allocation is used to guide AC and decide which slices are accepted. Formally, the long-timescale component sets the binary variables $x_s(t) \in \{0,1\}$ that indicate whether a service s is accepted at SLA block t .
- Then, at each T_{RA} time slot n within the SLA block t , the operator performs the actual allocation of resources for the admitted slices for the next RA block, leveraging a more accurate forecast that is limited to the shorter T interval. Formally, the short-timescale component defines $a_s(t,n)$, i.e., the percentage of the (predicted) traffic capacity that is to be reserved by MNO to slice s . Clearly, AC actions at longer timescales constrain and drive RA decisions at shorter timescales.

The design above lets kaNSaaS take advantage of traffic forecasting to spot gaps between the capacity requested by the SPs at each SLA block t and the future demand generated by the slices at every RA block (t, n) . Then, it uses suitable optimizers to maximize the MNO profit from the identified gaps via overbooking. From a technical viewpoint, kaNSaaS combines apt machine learning and optimization tools to implement each component.

Specifically, we adopt data-driven approaches to implement the prediction components at both short and long timescales since deep learning models have been largely proven to outperform statistical models in time series forecasting tasks [17]. The predicted demands are then fed to dedicated optimizers that take rapid, effective decisions on AC and RA based on an explainable logic.

4.1.1.2 *Solution based on loss meta-learning*

We consider that the QoE level determines certain monetary revenues and costs for the network operator, as follows. An SLA sets the performance target of a given network slice in terms of the requested end-user QoE and specifies the amount offered by the tenant for implementing the slice. The SLA also defines how such an amount is reduced for lower QoE levels, including an economic fee for the operator in case the QoE falls below a minimum acceptable threshold. Formally, let us denote the traffic demand generated by slice $s \in S$ at time t as $d_s(t)$ and its peak traffic demand as D_s , and let $c_s(t)$ be the amount of resources that the operator allocates to such a slice. We denote normalized demands and allocations as $\underline{d}_s(t) = d_s(t)/D_s$ and $\underline{c}_s(t) = c_s(t)/D_s$, respectively.

If the slice is accepted, the tenant pays for the implementation of the slice an amount $R_s(t) = \gamma d_s(t)$, which is proportional to the traffic to be accommodated by some constant γ factor (in \$/byte). However, the amount $R_s(t)$ is paid in full only if a target end-user QoE level is attained; if, instead, the end users suffer from lower QoE, the operator incurs a proportionally reduced payment by the tenant.

In our experiments, we assume that the QoE requirement is met if $\delta_s(t) = \underline{d}_s(t) - \underline{c}_s(t) \leq 0$, i.e., enough resources are reserved by the operator to serve the whole traffic demand of the slice. Otherwise, the QoE (hence the revenues for the operator) drops according to a sigmoid function of $\delta_s(t)$, as recommended by standard models [18] in revenue management and prospect theory [19]. Below a threshold QoE, the sigmoid becomes negative, meaning that the operator receives no payment but must start paying a fee to the tenant. If the QoE further falls below a minimum acceptable value, the fee jumps to a large amount $K_s(t) = \beta R_s(t)$ that is proportional to the requested resources for the slice. The resulting QoE-based cost of the accepted slice for the operator is

$$\text{QoE}(\delta_s(t)) = \left(\frac{K_s(t)}{2} (\tanh(\alpha \delta(t)) + \beta) + 1 \right) - R_s(t)$$

where α, β are constants that determine how the sigmoid function scales with the underprovisioning $\delta_s(t)$. Besides the revenue from the SLA, the total economic advantage of the operator is affected by two other elements. On the one hand, the overprovisioning of the reserved resources determines an increase in operating expenses (OPEX); therefore, whenever $\delta_s(t) < 0$, the operator incurs an OPEX penalty $-\gamma \delta_s(t)$ that grows linearly with the quantity of unnecessarily reserved resources. On the other hand, committing to allocate more resources than those available in the infrastructure leads to a global performance drop and possible service outages, with a huge cost M in terms of, e.g., customer churn.

The final performance cost associated with the slice MANO is

$$\mu = \sum_{s \in S} (\mathbf{1}(\underline{c}_s(t)) \cdot \text{QoE}(\delta_s(t)) - \mathbf{1}(-\delta_s(t)) \cdot \gamma \delta_s(t)) + M \cdot \mathbf{1}\left(\left(\sum_{s \in S} c_s(t)\right) - C\right)$$

where C is the total capacity of the system, and $\mathbf{1}(\cdot)$ is the step function that takes value zero if the argument is less than 0 and value one otherwise; thus, $\mathbf{1}(\underline{c}_s(t))$ takes value one only if the slice is admitted and resources are allocated to it.

A key observation is that, in practice, the network operator cannot analytically know the relation between the slice resource allocation and the QoE of end users of the specific tenant. This is a very complex function that depends on many operational parameters and whose characterization depends on application-level data (e.g., user feedback) that the operator does not have. Therefore, the first equation above is not known a priori in both its whole formulation and specific parametrization of α and β . In turn, this makes it impossible for the operator to model the whole performance cost in the second equation in advance.

In this scenario, the operator can apply the loss meta-learning architecture presented in Section 7.1.3 of D2.3 [3] to address the MANO task of deciding (i) which slices to accept and (ii) how many resources to reserve to accepted slices at the start of each orchestration interval. Indeed, once deployed in the system as an "AutoManager" component, loss meta-learning allows the comprehension of the expression of the performance cost in the second equation and optimizes the prediction of $\underline{c}_s(t)$ to minimize such cost. Note that the value of $\underline{c}_s(t)$ determines both the slice admission control via $\mathbf{1}(\underline{c}_s(t))$ and the allocation s of resources, which match its value if positive.

The detailed integration of such an AutoManager block in the overall network architecture is outlined in Figure 10. Our model sits in the Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (NFVO) of the MANO framework, as proposed by current standards. It can then leverage the Management Data Analytics Function (MDAF) to access information exposed via the Application Function (AF). Based on the operator-tenant agreement, such information can include live QoE measurements and slice revenue data, which let AutoManager observe the results of its decisions on the QoE and costs. Our model is then in a position to learn from experience the overall cost in the second equation above and forecast $\underline{c}_s(t)$, $\forall s \in S$ to minimize it.

Figure 10. Implementation of AutoManager in the network architecture to perform slice overbooking.

Figure 11. Sample of the final performance cost, in the naive case of a single slice in the network.

The meta-learning task is, in fact, not trivial. We provide an intuition of the complexity of the problem in Figure 11, which illustrates the expression in the second equation above in the naive case of a single slice. Despite the fact that we are considering the simplest version possible of the cost and the only one that can be represented in only three dimensions, the shape of the relationship between the MANO objective and the prediction is tangled and also highly sensitive to the value of the input traffic demand. Scaling to realistic, multidimensional versions of the cost thus implies very strong meta-learning capabilities.

4.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 9. Anticipatory capacity allocation with admission control usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The solutions described above leverage this interface to receive the relevant information about the status of the network. Specifically, relevant metrics that are communicated via Nio-Nifm are the resource utilization levels (in both approaches) and the network performance indicators (in the case of the loss meta-learning strategy). Additionally, the interface can be used to gather information related to the status of the NIFs so as to proactively optimize the NI optimization, e.g., by updating the operation timescale or even switching between the two solutions to the AC/RR problem identified above.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the different components of the algorithm, e.g., the probes to get network information or the Application Programming Interface (API) to enforce the resource allocation decision.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used for standard creation and termination procedures of NIF instances.

Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used jointly with the Nio-Nifcm to manage the resources associated with the NI function. As both approaches leverage neural networks, the availability of dedicated hardware, such as GPUs, is expected. The optimization problems adopted by the hybrid solution only require a CPU to run a standard solver.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to trigger re-training of the different neural networks adopted in the two solutions. In the case of the hybrid model, this is an on-demand operation based on, e.g., monitoring of the quality of the decisions. In the case of a meta-learning approach, re-training is triggered at the model deployment stage since the relationship between the decision and performance must be learned from system operations.
Mlo-Ncat	This interface allows access to the model register, thus enabling storage and retrieval of trained neural networks for both solutions above. This is especially critical in the case of the loss meta-learning strategy, as it allows fetching already trained loss neural networks, which can be employed (and further trained) in contexts where similar, but not identical relationships between decision and performance are expected (e.g., AC/RR under a different set of slices).
Nio-Mano	This interface is critical in the use case under scrutiny, as it enables direct communication and control from the NIO to the MANO framework, thus enabling NI decisions to be enacted in terms of slice control via the associated MANO operations.
Nio-Ext	This interface can be used when slice control spans multiple domains, i.e., slices are not domain-specific but operate end-to-end. In those cases, the interface allows the NIO to allocate NI instances in diverse domains of the network, hence composing a complex NIS that performs AC and RR in an end-to-end (or multi-domain in all cases) fashion.

4.1.2.2 *Usage of NIO procedures and elements*

We detail in this subsection how this NI solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is, for instance, initiated when a solution for slice AC/RR using overbooking that is based on expert knowledge (e.g., the one outlined in Section 4.1.1.1) starts to under-perform, indicating that the relationship between the decisions taken by the model and the resulting system performance is changing. Therefore, the NIO decides to switch to a new model capable of coping with the evolving relationship above.
2. The NIO checks the NIS Catalog and identifies a model based on a meta-learning approach (e.g., the one outlined in Section 4.1.1.2), which can learn the new relationship between decision and performance metric.
3. The model is validated and deployed for meta-learning while producing decisions through the Nio-Mano and Nifm-Nifnis interfaces.
4. The MANO system acknowledges the new operation mode. Note that once the updated loss is meta-learned, it can be communicated back to human experts for the design of an effective (e.g., hybrid) decision-making solution.

4.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 10. Anticipatory capacity allocation with admission control. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-CFORE-000	Effective (90%)	These solutions contribute to the overall capability of anticipating in an automated manner the amount of network resources that are required to accommodate future mobile service demands. Their operation is detailed above and in previous deliverables, D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2] of the project, and their performance will be presented in the future D5.3 of the project.
FR-CFORE-002	Successful (100%)	The solutions for slicing AC/RR accounts by design for the monetary costs incurred by the operator, as detailed in their operation above.
FR-CFORE-005	Successful (95%)	One of the NI solutions proposed for network slice AC/RR builds on the full loss meta-learning design presented in Section 7.1.3 of D2.3. It thus contributes to meeting the requirement of the learning loss function in an automated fashion. Evidence of the effectivity will be provided in D5.3 of the project, which will allow achieving 100% of FR-CFORE-005.

4.2 Virtual Machine reservation under meta-learned loss

In Section 4.2 of D4.1 [1], [3], we presented a NI to address the problem of Virtual Machine (VM) reservation, which was then further detailed in Section 3.2 of D4.2 [2]. Specifically, in this capacity forecasting use case, we consider a core network data center setting, where we assume that different video streaming services are assigned a dedicated Network Slice Subnet Instance (NSSI). This requires a prediction of the number of VMs that need to be allocated in advance to each NSSI so as to run the VNFs required to serve the demand generated by the corresponding mobile service. Clearly, every VM has an operating cost (e.g., due to power consumption), so it is desirable that only the strictly necessary set of VMs is reserved for each NSSI.

4.2.1 Solution description

We refer the reader to Section 4.2 of D4.1 [1] for a complete description of the solution.

4.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 11. Virtual Machine reservation under meta-learned loss usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The solutions described above leverage this interface to receive the relevant information about the status of the network. Specifically, relevant metrics that are communicated via Nio-Nifm are the VM resource utilization levels.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the different components of the algorithm, e.g., the probes to get network information or the API to enforce the resource allocation decision.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used for standard creation and termination procedures of NIF instances.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used jointly with the Nio-Nifcm to manage the resources associated with the NI function. As the proposed approach leverages neural networks, the availability of dedicated hardware, such as GPUs, is expected.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to trigger re-training of the different neural networks adopted in the solution. As we propose a meta-learning approach, re-training is triggered at the model deployment stage since the relationship between the decision and performance must be learned from system operations.
Mio-Ncat	This interface allows access to the model register, thus enabling storage and retrieval of trained neural networks. This is especially critical for the loss meta-learning strategy used by the NI solution, as it allows fetching already trained loss neural networks, which can be employed (and possibly further trained) in contexts where similar, but not identical relationships between decision and performance are expected (e.g., tackling the same problem at a different datacenter in the network).
Nio-Mano	This interface is critical in the use case under scrutiny, as it enables direct communication and control from the NIO to the MANO framework, thus enabling NI decisions to be enacted in terms of VM control via the associated MANO operations.
Nio-Ext	This interface is not used in this use case, as no communication across domains or beyond the mobile network infrastructure is envisioned.

4.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this NI solution leverages the knowledge-sharing procedure discussed in Section 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3] with respect to the NI for minimization of video streaming slice OPEX that will be outlined in Section 4.3 of this document.

1. This procedure is initiated when both the VM reservation NIS presented above and the NIS for allocation of computing resources to slices associated with video streaming services described in Section 4.3 of this deliverable need to be run at the network core datacenter (VM reservation) and Edge compute facility (video streaming slice resource allocation).
2. As these NIS employ the same knowledge, i.e., the volume of traffic generated by specific individual services, their concurrent operation creates a case for knowledge sharing across NIS. This is initially verified by checking the parameters of the NIS against the Policy Interpreter and Configuration (PolicyIC). Once the PolicyIC receives the resolution, the new NIS domain-specific policies are built and applied.

3. With the updated NIS descriptor, the NIS Creation Selection Optimization and Instantiation (CSOI) requests the translation of the external domain knowledge to the Model Explainability block. As a result, the NIS CSOI receives the additional Knowledge rules.
4. The NIS CSOI sends the NIS descriptor again to the PolicyIC, but this time together with Knowledge rules in order to build and apply the shared knowledge policies for the volume of data traffic generated by the specific (video streaming) individual services. This is realized via interactions between the CSOI and PolicyIC, as described in Section 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3].
5. Finally, the NIO acknowledges the NIS deployment to the sender.

4.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 12. Virtual Machine reservation under meta-learned loss. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-CFORE-000	Effective (90%)	This NI solution contributes to the overall capability of anticipating in an automated manner the amount of network resources that are required to accommodate future mobile service demands. Its operation is detailed in previous deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2] of the project, and their performance is presented in Section 4.5.2 of D5.2 [20] of the project.
FR-CFORE-002	Successful (100%)	The solution for VM reservation accounts by design for the monetary costs incurred by the operator, as detailed in D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2].
FR-CFORE-005	Successful (95%)	This NI builds on a loss meta-learning design presented in Section 4.1.3 of D2.2 [21], which allows learning loss functions as set out by requirement FR-CFORE-005. Demonstrations of the effectiveness of the approach are provided by the results in Section 4.5.2 of D5.2 [20].

4.3 Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX with meta-learned loss

In Section 4.3 of D4.1 [1], we presented an NI to address the problem of minimizing OPEX associated with video streaming slices, which was then further detailed in Section 3.3 of D4.2 [2]. Specifically, in this capacity forecasting use case, we target a mobile Edge environment where a set of computational facilities, each serving several tens of BSs, are located close to the radio access. We assume that different video streaming services with dedicated NSSI run at the Edge facilities. Here, the management intent aims at minimizing the monetary OPEX associated with running the video streaming slices at the network Edge. This maps to an objective of periodically and preemptively rescaling the compute resources assigned to each NSSI in a facility to smoothly run the needed VNFs.

4.3.1 Solution description

We refer the reader to Section 4.3 of D4.1 [1] for a complete description of the solution.

4.3.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.3.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 13. Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX with meta-learned loss usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The solutions described above leverage this interface to receive the relevant information about the status of the network. Specifically, relevant metrics that are communicated via Nio-Nifm are the slice resource utilization and demand levels.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the different components of the algorithm, e.g., the probes to get network information or the API to enforce the resource allocation decision.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used for standard creation and termination procedures of NIF instances.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used jointly with the Nio-Nifcm to manage the resources associated with the NI function. As the proposed approach leverages neural networks, the availability of dedicated hardware, such as GPUs, is expected.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to trigger re-training of the different neural networks adopted in the solution. As we propose a meta-learning approach, re-training is triggered at the model deployment stage since the relationship between the decision and performance must be learned from system operations.

Mio-Ncat	This interface allows access to the model register, thus enabling storage and retrieval of trained neural networks. This is especially critical for the loss meta-learning strategy used by the NI solution, as it allows fetching already trained loss neural networks, which can be employed (and possibly further trained) in contexts where similar, but not identical relationships between decision and performance are expected (e.g., tackling the same problem at a different datacenter in the network).
Nio-Mano	This interface is critical in the use case under scrutiny, as it enables direct communication and control from the NIO to the MANO framework, thus enabling NI decisions to be enacted in terms of VM control via the associated MANO operations.
Nio-Ext	This interface can be used when slice control spans multiple domains, i.e., slices are not domain-specific but operate end-to-end. In those cases, the interface allows the NIO to allocate NI instances in diverse domains of the network, hence composing a complex NIS that performs slice optimization in an end-to-end (or multi-domain in all cases) fashion.

4.3.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

An example of the usage of NIO procedures and elements with this NI solution is presented in Section 4.2.2.2 above. In that section, we detail how the NI solution can leverage the knowledge-sharing procedure discussed in Section 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3] with respect to the NI for VM reservation outlined in Section 4.2 of this same deliverable.

4.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 14. Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX with meta-learned loss. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-CFORE-000	Effective (90%)	This NI solution contributes to the overall capability of anticipating in an automated manner the amount of network resources that are required to accommodate future mobile service demands. Its operation is detailed in previous deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2] of the project, and their performance is presented in Section 4.5.3 of D5.2 [20].
FR-CFORE-002	Successful (100%)	The solution for the anticipatory allocation of computing resources to video streaming slices accounts by design for the monetary costs incurred by the operator, as detailed in D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2].
FR-CFORE-005	Successful (95%)	This NI builds on a loss meta-learning design presented in Section 4.1.3 of D2.2 [21], which allows learning loss functions as set out by requirement FR-CFORE-005. Demonstrations of the effectiveness of the approach are provided by the results in Section 4.5.3 of D5.2 [20].

4.4 Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing

4.4.1 Solution description

This work addresses the discrete caching (prefetching) problem: choose files to replicate in a local cache to maximize the probability that a new file request is served locally. Hitting the cache optimizes user experience in Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) and enhances the performance of wireless networks. Our solution aspires to advance the theoretical understanding and proposes new provably-optimal and computationally-efficient caching algorithms using a new approach based on optimistic learning.

Figure 12. Optimistic online caching with predictions: system (left) & algorithm template (right).

Common caching policies store the newly requested files and employ the Least-Recently-Used (LRU), Least-Frequently-Used (LFU) and other similar rules to evict files when the cache capacity is exhausted. Under certain statistical assumptions on the request trace, such policies maintain the cache at an optimal state. However, with the frequent addition of new content to libraries and the high volatility of file popularity, these policies can perform arbitrarily badly. This has spurred research efforts for policies that

operate under more general conditions. Our goal is to design robust policies that are able to learn effective caching decisions with the aid of a prediction oracle of unknown quality (see Figure 12 left).

Model. We formulate the caching problem as an online convex optimization (OCO) problem. At each slot $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, a learner (the caching policy) selects a caching vector $x_t \in X$ from the set of admissible cache states $X \subseteq \{0,1\}^N$ for a cache of size C , where N is the library size. Then, a 1-hot vector $\theta_t \in \{0,1\}^N$ with value 1 for the requested file is revealed, and the learner receives a reward of $f_t(x_t) = \langle \theta_t, x_t \rangle$ for cache hits. The reward is revealed only after committing x_t , which naturally matches the dynamic caching operation where the cached files are decided before the next request arrives. Here, the learner makes no statistical assumptions and θ_t can follow any distribution, even one that is handpicked by an adversary. In the optimistic framework, the learner does not only consider his hit-or-miss performance so far when deciding x_t , but also the predictor's performance and output (Figure 12 right). We characterize the policy's performance by using the static regret metric:

$$R_T(\{x\}_T) = \sup_{\{f_t\}_{t=1}^T} \{\sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x^*) - \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_t)\},$$

where $x^* = \arg \max_{x \in X} \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x)$ is the (typically unknown) *best-in-hindsight* cache decision that can be selected only with access to future requests. An algorithm is said to achieve sublinear regret when its average performance gap $\frac{R_T}{T}$ vanishes as $T \rightarrow \infty$.

Achievable regret for Caching with a Predictor. Our first result demonstrates the best achievable regret in the setup we consider, which turns out to be $R_T = \Omega\left(\left[\sum_{t=1}^T \|\theta_t - \tilde{\theta}_t\|_2^2\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)$, indicating a significant potential of obtaining a regret that scales with the predictor's error rather than the time horizon T . In general, the predictions refer to the next function $\tilde{f}_t(\cdot)$. However, since most OCO algorithms learn based on the observed gradients, it suffices to have predictions $\tilde{\theta}_t = \nabla \tilde{f}_t(x_t)$. For caching, this coincides with a prediction for the next request. In fact, this model can be readily generalized to other linear utilities beyond cache-hits so as to incorporate, e.g., file-specific caching gains time-varying network conditions. Here, $\tilde{\theta}_t$ is a probability distribution over the library.

Theorem. For any online caching policy, there exists a sequence of requests $\{\theta_t\}_T$ and predictions $\{\tilde{\theta}_t\}$ for which the regret R_T satisfies

$$E[R_T] \geq \sqrt{\frac{C}{2\pi}} \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T \|\theta_t - \tilde{\theta}_t\|_2^2} - \Theta\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}\right).$$

Caching through Optimistic Regularization (OFTRL-Cache). The gist of our approach here is that we use OFTRL to obtain $\hat{x} \in \text{conv}(X)$, and then apply Madow's sampling scheme to recover integral caching vectors $x_t \in X$ which satisfies the hard capacity non-convex constraint. In other words, we define $X = \{x \in \{0,1\}^N \mid \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \leq C\}$, where N is the set of unit-sized files (library) and C is the cache capacity (in file units); and $x_i = 1$ decides to cache file $i \in N$. Let us define the prediction error at slot t as $\delta_t = \|\theta_t - \tilde{\theta}_t\|_2^2$, and introduce the proximal σ_t -strongly convex regularizer w.r.t. the Euclidean ℓ_2 norm $r_t(x) = \frac{\sigma_t}{2} \|x - x_t\|_2^2$. We also define parameters $\{\sigma_t\}_t$ using the accumulated prediction errors, namely:

$\sigma_1 = \sigma\sqrt{\delta_1}$, $\sigma_t = \sigma(\sqrt{\delta_{1:t}} - \sqrt{\delta_{1:t-1}})$, $\forall t \geq 2$, with $\sigma_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{C}}$. The detailed steps are summarized in Figure 13. The regret guarantee of the OFTRL-Cache algorithm is described next.

Algorithm 1: OFTRL-Cache

```

1 Input:  $\sigma = 1/\sqrt{C}$ ,  $\delta_1 = \|\theta_1 - \tilde{\theta}_1\|_2^2$ ,  $\sigma_1 = \sigma\sqrt{\delta_1}$ ,  $x_1 = \arg \min_{x \in X} \langle x, \theta_1 \rangle$ 
2 Output:  $\{x_t \in X\}_T$ 
3 for  $t = 2, 3, \dots$  do
4    $\tilde{\theta}_t \leftarrow$  prediction // Obtain request prediction for slot  $t$ 
5    $\hat{x}_t = \arg \max_{x \in \text{conv}(X)} \{-r_{1:t-1}(x) + \langle x, \theta_{t-1} + \tilde{\theta}_t \rangle\}$ 
6    $x_t \leftarrow \text{MadowSample}(\hat{x}_t)$ 
7    $\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + \tilde{\theta}_t$  // Receive  $t$ -slot request and update total gradient
8    $\sigma_t = \sigma(\sqrt{\delta_{1:t}} - \sqrt{\delta_{1:t-1}})$  // Update the regularization parameter
end
```

Figure 13. Algorithm 1: OFTRL-Cache pseudocode.

Theorem. OFTRL-Cache ensures, for any time horizon T and $N \geq 2C$, the expected regret bound:

$$E[R_T] \leq 2\sqrt{C} \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T \|\theta_t - \tilde{\theta}_t\|_2^2}.$$

The bound in this theorem *shrinks* with the prediction quality. If all predictions are accurate, we get $R_T \leq 0$; when all predictions fail, we get $R_T \leq 2\sqrt{2CT}$. That is, in the worst scenario, the regret bound is worse by a constant factor of $\sqrt{2}$ compared to the FTRL algorithm that does not use predictions. Moreover, the bounds are dimension-free and do not depend on the library size N .

Caching through Optimistic Perturbations (OFTPL-Cache). We propose next a new OFTPL algorithm that is of independent interest with potential applications that extend beyond caching to other k -set structured problems. The steps of the proposed scheme are presented in t , where we denote the $y_t \in X$ -slot OFTPL decisions with $y_t \in X$. The following theorem characterizes the performance of the new OFTPL.

Algorithm 2: OFTPL-Cache

```

1 Input:  $\eta_1 = 0, y_1 = \arg \min_{y \in X} \langle y, \theta_1 \rangle$ 
2 Output:  $\{y_t \in X\}_T$ 
3  $\gamma \stackrel{iid}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1_{N \times 1})$  // Sample a perturbation vector
4 for  $t = 2, 3, \dots$  do
5    $\hat{\theta}_t \leftarrow$  prediction // Obtain request prediction for slot  $t$ 
6    $\eta_t = \frac{1.3}{\sqrt{C}} \left( \frac{1}{\ln(Ne/C)} \right)^{1/4} \sqrt{\sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} \|\theta_\tau - \hat{\theta}_\tau\|_1^2}$  // Update the pert. param.
7    $y_t = \arg \max_{y \in X} \langle y, \Theta_{t-1} + \hat{\theta}_t + \eta_t \gamma \rangle$  // Update the cache vector
8    $\Theta_t = \Theta_{t-1} + \theta_t$  // Receive request for  $t$  and update total gradient
end

```

Figure 14. Algorithm 2: OFTPL-Cache pseudocode.

Theorem. OFTPL-Cache ensures, for any time horizon T and $N \geq 2C$ with $C \geq 11$, expected regret bound:

$$E_\gamma[R_T] \leq 3.68 \sqrt{C} \left(\ln \frac{Ne}{C} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T \|\theta_t - \hat{\theta}_t\|_1^2}.$$

The regret bound here is also modulated with the quality of predictions: it collapses to zero when predictions are perfect and maintains $R_T \leq 3.68 \ln \left(\frac{Ne}{C} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T \|\theta_t - \hat{\theta}_t\|_2^2}$ for arbitrary bad predictions.

Compared with the previous theorem, OFTPL achieves regret bounds worse by a factor of $\sim 1.9 \ln \left(\frac{Ne}{C} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}}$, which depends on N , albeit in a small order. However, OFTPL-Cache does not involve the expensive projection operation in OFTRL-Cache, rather a simple quantile-finding operation (top C files).

4.4.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.4.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 15. Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, NIO gathers information on the cache hit ratio of the solution and monitors the state of the solution.
Nio-Nifcm	Through this interface, NIO can restrict the algorithm in the solution to choose the caching decisions from a given subset by considering the space limitations.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used to create and instantiate the predictors and share the caching decisions of the algorithm with the NIF manager.
Nifcm-Nivi	Through this interface, OFTRL-Cache and OFTPL-Cache algorithms can share the decisions on the frequency of requested predictions by taking into consideration the computation resources.
Nio-MLp	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Nio-Mano	Through this interface, NIO can decide on different predictors depending on the loss.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with other O-RAN components to employ the cache decisions produced by the solution.

4.4.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management and the knowledge-sharing procedures discussed in Sections 5.1.3 and 5.2.2 of D2.3 [3].

- OFTRL-Cache and OFTPL-Cache algorithms obtain the predictions of the system state through the knowledge-sharing procedure.

- By using these predictions, the two algorithms in this solution produce the optimal caching decisions to manage the NIF.

4.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 16. Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-CFORE-000	Successful (100%)	As discussed in Section 3.4.1 of D4.2 [2], this solution contributes to meeting the requirement of designing models for capacity prediction that support NI algorithms across the mobile network architecture.
FR-CFORE-003	Successful (100%)	As discussed in Section 4.4.1, this solution operates over streaming data.
FR-CFORE-005	Successful (100%)	DAEMON's Capacity Forecasting (CFORE) shall be able to learn autonomously their objective/loss function. OFTPL-Cache algorithm described in this solution satisfies this requirement.

5 Automated anomaly response

In Section 4 of D4.2 [2], we introduced four distinct solutions aimed at addressing anomalies across various components of the cellular ecosystem, including the RAN, base stations, and the international interconnection network between mobile operators. In this section, we provide further updates and explain the integration of the solutions to the NI plane defined in WP2.

5.1 Federated learning powered anomaly detection in B5G/6G

5.1.1 Solution description

In D4.2, Section 4.1, [2], the initial description of the Federated Learning (FL)-powered anomaly detection algorithm was presented, leveraging the DBSCAN and CART algorithms towards a hybrid approach, in which unsupervised learning is used at different timescales and requests for new incoming data at each FL client, while rule-based anomaly detection is performed for real-time operation. The above introduces several challenges with regard to the agent-controller synchronization, signaling efficiency, as well as agent-based rule-based classification optimization aspects. Those are tackled by this deliverable.

5.1.1.1 Addressing the challenges

The characteristic feature of the highly dynamic systems we examine is that the spread of data points tends to change over time, which could affect the overall clustering outcome and potentially cause the misclassification of legitimate data points as outliers or vice versa. Thus, we describe in this section a solution that dynamically adapts the *epsilon* and *minPts* parameters (as thoroughly initially described in the context of D4.2 [2]). However, adapting the *epsilon* and *minPts* parameters continuously is computationally demanding. So, we follow an approach that accommodates the dual requirement of accurate clustering and the efficient use of computational resources. This approach is based on calculating the Local Density Variance (LDV) of each point to dynamically update the *eps* and *MinPts* variables of the algorithm. LDV serves as an indicator of how the local density around data points changes; a larger LDV implies that the local density around data points is changing drastically, while a smaller LDV suggests that the local density is relatively stable.

The utility of the LDV is double. Primarily, it provides a means to track the performance of the clustering algorithm as an increasing LDV could be an indicator that the clustering algorithm is beginning to find it challenging to correctly classify points, which may hint that it's time to adjust the *epsilon* and *minPts* parameters. Additionally, the LDV can assist in deciding *when* to modify the parameters. As said, changing the parameters is computationally intensive, so the frequency of the transmission of update messages must be minimized. On the other hand, very long inactive periods of updates should also be avoided because the likelihood of misclassification could rise. Therefore, the parameters should be adjusted whenever the LDV increases beyond a certain threshold, *T*. This guarantees a quick response to data changes whilst minimizing the computational cost.

The rationale for the use of this metric is that the points near the center of a cluster would typically have a higher local density, but their impact on the LDV would depend on how the local densities around other points are changing. If the local densities around points are generally stable (i.e., not changing much), then the LDV will be low, regardless of whether some points have a high local density. On the other hand, if local densities around points are changing drastically, then the LDV will be high. Therefore, this metric gives the algorithm more robustness regarding observing changes in the data over time and helps it maintain a good performance in identifying clusters and outliers in dynamic data.

To calculate LDV, we first calculate the local density of each point, which is determined by the number of points within a certain radius (*epsilon*). For instance, if we denote $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}]$ the set of all data points, the density of each point will be as follows:

$$D(p_i) = \frac{1}{\text{card}(\{p_j \mid d(p_i, p_j) \leq \text{eps}, j \neq i\})}$$

where $d(p_i, p_j)$ is the Euclidean distance between points p_i and p_j and *eps* is the current maximum distance for two points to be considered in the same neighborhood. The mean and *D* will be as follows:

$$E[D] = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_i D(p_i)$$

Once we have these local densities, we compute their variance, which gives us the LDV.

$$\text{LDV} = V[D] = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_i D(p_i)^2 - E[D]^2$$

If the LDV has increased by a certain threshold, T , we take that as an indication that the data's density characteristics have significantly changed. To adapt to the change, we adjust ϵ and minPts as follows:

- We reduce ϵ by setting it to the average distance between each point and its $K = \text{minPts}$ nearest neighbors. Decreasing ϵ makes the neighborhood around a data point smaller. This makes sense when data points start becoming denser, i.e., more points start appearing close together. With a smaller ϵ value, the algorithm can distinguish between dense regions (clusters) and sparse regions (outliers) more effectively. Thus, by adaptively decreasing ϵ when local density increases, we ensure that the algorithm remains sensitive to the evolving density of the data, thus improving its ability to detect clusters and outliers. On the other hand, if the data points start becoming sparser, it may be useful to increase ϵ to capture larger neighborhoods.
- We increase minPts by a certain amount, e.g., by one unit, for the sake of simplicity. This makes it harder for points to form a cluster, thus preventing the algorithm from creating many small clusters in high-density areas. By increasing minPts , we ensure that a region needs to have more points to be considered a cluster, thus avoiding the misclassification of noisy regions as clusters.

5.1.1.2 *Outlier blending*

The core idea we propose is a modification of the DBSCAN clustering algorithm that takes into account the temporal evolution of the data. Given that new points are generated continuously, these new data points could affect the overall clustering result and might cause true outliers to blend with regular data points. This phenomenon poses a significant challenge in maintaining the integrity of the clustering process. Our proposed solution involves removing older points from the dataset periodically and then rerunning the DBSCAN clustering algorithm.

The process of removing older data points and rerunning the clustering algorithm can be computationally expensive. Therefore, we propose a method that balances the need for accurate clustering and the computational resources available. This method is guided by a metric that we call average anomaly score (AAS) that serves as a measure of "how anomalous" the outliers are; a higher AAS means that the outliers exhibit a very different behavior from the normal points, whereas a lower AAS suggests that the outliers are beginning to blend with the normal points.

The use of the AAS serves two purposes in our proposed method. Firstly, it allows us to monitor the performance of the clustering algorithm. A decreasing AAS can be a warning sign that our clustering algorithm is starting to struggle to separate normal points from outliers, which could suggest that it's time to remove old points and rerun the clustering algorithm. Secondly, the AAS can guide the decision of when to rerun the clustering algorithm. Running the clustering algorithm is computationally expensive, so the running frequency must not be too high. On the other hand, very low running frequency is not a preferable option either because the phenomenon of mixing outliers as inliers could start becoming more prominent. Therefore, the clustering algorithm should rerun whenever the AAS decreases by a certain threshold T . This ensures that we react quickly to changes in the data, while also minimizing the computational cost.

For a specific state of the system, let us denote the set of outliers $O = [o_1, o_2, \dots, o_{|O|}]$ as well as the set of all the core points $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{|C|}]$. The Euclidean distance from an outlier point o_j to its nearest core point is defined as follows:

$$D_j = \min_i d(o_j, c_i)$$

Therefore, the AAS is measured as the average of these distances for all outlier points as follows:

$$\text{AAS} = \frac{1}{|O|} \sum_j D_j$$

The AAS metric allows us to focus on the expansion of the cluster, which in turn may indicate a rise in the number of outliers that blend with the inliers, potentially signifying a shift in the normal state of the system. Thus, the DBSCAN clustering algorithm will be triggered when the AAS decreases by $T\%$. Therefore given that the relative change in the AAS between two consecutive time snapshots is denoted by $\Delta = \frac{\text{AAS}_t - \text{AAS}_{t-1}}{\text{AAS}_{t-1}}$, the algorithm will rerun if and only if $\Delta \leq -T$. Note that when the algorithm reruns, it will take into account only the points generated in the last τ time steps to ensure that the clustering process stays up to date and outliers are continuing to be identified relative to the current state of the system and not its past state to avoid outlier blending. Thus, given that each point is assigned a timestamp on generation and the set of all points is denoted by $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}]$, the set of the remained points will be $P' = \{p_i | p_i^{\text{time}} \geq t_{\text{now}} - \tau, p_i \in P\}$.

This approach assumes that a legitimate expansion of the cluster, i.e., more inliers appearing at its edges, is generally healthy, while an expansion driven by what were previously considered outliers indicates a drift in the underlying data structure that requires action.

5.1.1.3 Agent-Controller Synchronization

Agent-controller synchronization is one of the key challenges that need to be addressed, as this issue is central to the efficacy of the FL system and plays a significant role in its overall performance. The main difficulty of this challenge lies in achieving seamless synchronization in a geographically large, distributed network where individual FL clients and the FL controller must interact efficiently and in a timely manner. This can lead to disparities in the execution of FL processes across different agents, which may further result in outdated information at the controller that runs the CART algorithm that could possibly have an impact on the reliability and accuracy of the anomaly detection proposed solution.

To overcome these challenges, the implementation of time synchronization techniques, such as Precision Time Protocol (PTP), can be beneficial. These protocols are designed to synchronize the clocks of clients over variable-latency data networks, thus ensuring a consistent time frame across all participating clients and the central controller.

Additionally, we suggest exploring asynchronous FL approaches that allow the central server to aggregate model updates as and when they are received from the clients, removing the need for strict synchronization. Such an approach can alleviate the impact of slower agents and network latency, thus improving the overall efficiency and robustness of the FL system.

5.1.1.4 Signaling Efficiency

Another key challenge in the FL system is ensuring signaling efficiency. Given the potentially large number of agents involved in the FL network, there is a significant amount of signaling overhead associated with communications between the clients and the central controller. This overhead becomes particularly prominent when the server needs to broadcast updates to all agents or collect local updates from them.

This challenge can have significant implications on the system. For instance, an increase in signaling overhead can strain network resources, potentially causing network congestion (increased packet drop rate), hence increasing latency and synchronization issues. These issues can significantly degrade the performance of the system, possibly leading to inaccurate anomaly detection (due to the affected sync) or increased energy consumption (due to retransmissions because of the packet losses).

Addressing this challenge requires a comprehensive strategy that encompasses the use of efficient communication protocols and techniques designed to mitigate signaling overhead. To this direction, as also described in D4.2 [2], certain conditions have been applied for an agent to “qualify” for transmitting the local outlier and border point data sets to the central controller. This can be classified under the adaptive client sampling methodology category, namely, techniques in which the central server communicates with a subset of clients in each communication round, reducing the amount of signaling and associated overhead. The subset of clients can be selected based on various factors, such as their data distribution, availability, or network conditions.

5.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

5.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 17. Federated Learning-powered Anomaly Detection usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	This interface is used to provide learning- and network-based monitoring information towards the FL agent-specific clustering performance (e.g., Silhouette score-based information, AAS, etc.), the data volume-related statistics (directly linked to the weighting of each FL agent), as well as the recurrent fine-tuning process of epsilon and MinPts values, as described above towards outlier blending minimization. FL agent selection and NIF instances orchestration (including initialization and termination of certain FL agents, according to performance) is also leveraging this interface.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the distributed (i.e., FL agent-based NIF instances) and central FL controller resource allocation-related configuration and enforcement.
Nifm-Nifnis	Based on the FL agent selection and NIS resource allocation decisions made by the NI Orchestrator, this interface is used for the instantiation and termination of the respective NIF instances at the distributed FL agents.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used to interact with the virtualized resources associated with the distributed and centralized NIF operations (i.e., FL agents and centralized controller).
Nio-MLp	This interface is used by the centralized FL controller in order to trigger re-training of the CART-based model to be re-forwarded to the distributed agents for anomaly detection/inference. This is an on-demand operation based on the NIF performance monitored and reported via the Nio-Nifm interface, such as the AAS information monitored and calculated at various intervals.

Mlo-Ncat	This interface allows access to the model register, thus enabling storage and retrieval of the various distributed DBSCAN, as well as centralized CART models.
Nio-Mano	This interface is used in order to communicate the NIF-specific outputs, i.e., detected anomalies from the different FL agents and aggregated and reported via the centralized controller) towards the MANO component in order to consider them for the respective network management and orchestration operations.
Nio-Ext	This interface can be used when the distributed FL agents span across multiple domains to monitor NIF performance and reporting to the centralized FL controller and NIO.

5.1.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

The orchestration and management of the FL-powered anomaly detection NIS relies on several inter- and intra-NIO procedures:

- Upon NIS creation, it should be verified that all the DBSCAN- and CART-related NIFs are available in the NIS Catalog and the respective NI Function and Service Descriptors (NIFDs/NISDs) are created. Learning-related metrics required for the lifecycle management and orchestration of the NIS are also defined in the context of this procedure, such as the Silhouette score, AAS, etc.
- DBSCAN-based NIF instantiation and deployment to relevant distributed nodes, according to NIO resource allocation policies. Feasibility check of the distributed NIFs interconnection, acknowledgment of the instantiation, etc., is part of those procedures.
- NIF update requests are realized according to and as part of the NIO Data Analytics component and recurrent calculation of the NIS performance metrics (AAS, Silhouette score, etc.); this primarily regards the distributed NIFs. As far as the centralized NIF is concerned (the CART-based operations), resource scaling is in scope according to the data volume and number of FL agents-related requirements (and respective computing requirements).
- Termination, temporary disabling of an FL agent (e.g., due to energy constraints, etc.), is also part of the NIO procedures.

Knowledge sharing of one domain-specific controller (CART-based model) across domains to similar FL-based setups is also in scope.

5.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 18. Federated learning powered anomaly detection in B5G/6G. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-AARES-000	Successful (100%)	This NI Functionality uses FL-powered anomaly detection capabilities to identify diverse types of anomalous network KPI and computing resource-related behavior.
FR-AARES-001	Successful (100%)	This NI Functionality requires the detection anomaly NIS to be able to operate at different timescales. The FL agents performing DBSCAN-based anomaly collection, as well as the CART-based inference model distributed from the centralized controller to the FL agents, depend on the monitored data of the respective volume and are not constrained in terms of timescale. The centralized model is also independently updated on a configurable basis, regardless of the client ratio that has provided its locally trained model's output.
FR-AARES-003	Successful (100%)	This NI functionality requires that the anomaly detection model take into account the cost of the system in terms of resources towards an efficient and feasible anomaly detection solution. This FL-powered solution enables high scalability, initiating and terminating in a flexible manner the FL agents that participate in the distributed process while also without the need to increase the network traffic monitoring overhead due to data exchange and signaling minimization steps; additionally, the low complexity ML model that has been employed leads to low energy costs per-client (DBSCAN), but also at the central FL controller side (CART-based approach).

5.2 Proactive anomaly detection for IoT services in a global roaming platform

5.2.1 Solution description

5.2.1.1 Experience with the previous versions of ANCHOR

Signaling Matrices. In an incipient phase of ANCHOR design (which we presented in Deliverable 4.1 [1] and 4.2 [2]), we drew from the idea that deep learning's success is mainly due to its ability to learn good representations from complex unstructured data, such as the signaling data we collect from the IoT provider infrastructure. We thus chose to focus on the signaling volume and encoded the signaling event's volume in a representation similar to images (which are generally suitable for deep learning models). We generated signaling matrices, where the rows represent different protocol-specific features (e.g., the MAP/Diameter request types), and the columns represent time intervals. Following this logic, for example, we grouped the values of "dialogue duration" by defining ranges that differentiate between normal and unusual values so that the model can discriminate easily between these values. In this case, a duration larger than 2,500 ms would be considered unusual while being above 6 seconds would be rare. For each level we encode (and add as a row in the signaling matrix), we then generate counters for presence within the time intervals we encode into each column of the signaling matrix.

Sequential representation. We test a new data representation designed for sequence-to-sequence (Seq2Seq) models [3], [22] to take advantage of the temporal patterns within the data. Seq2Seq models have become popular for applications such as speech-to-text [23], text-to-speech, and neural machine translation [24], [25]. This model uses a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to map the input sequence to a vector of fixed dimensionality and then another deep LSTM to decode the target sequence from the vector. The LSTM's ability to successfully learn on data with long-range temporal dependencies makes it a natural choice for this application due to the time lag between samples. The input to the Seq2Seq model are three different vectors: the encoded sequences of request types and result codes (*codes x*); its corresponding timestamps *t*; and the difference between consecutive timestamps, which we call *deltas*. We encode deltas by using the same mapping we used for duration, and consider an extra category when the previous code is from a different day.

With the two data representation approaches above, we evaluated the anomaly detection engine on ground-truth anomalies that we collected in January 2020, which we presented in D5.1 [26]. We focused on two days (i.e., January 14th and January 20th) and analyzed the top 15 devices in the rank of anomaly scores for each cluster and each model. Specifically, we verify with the operation teams if the devices belonging to this list actually had anomalous behavior, if they were present in the ticketing system, or if their behavior (though different from "normal") was not harmful. First, we found that a large fraction of devices do not present a harmful behavior despite it being different from their normal trends. Finally, we found the CNN-VAE is the model that is able to detect the highest number of novel anomalies within the top 15 ranked devices in order of their anomaly score.

Based on the manner of representing our signaling information, most anomalies ANCHOR detects were related to aggressive signaling behavior from IoT devices. In fact, thanks to ANCHOR, we were able to detect IoT devices that were stressing the visited networks to the extent of endangering the commercial roaming agreement these had with the home operator supporting the IoT provider. These devices were generating large volumes of signaling against local providers in an attempt to complete the attach procedure.

However useful, this initial version of ANCHOR was limited to focusing only on anomalies related to the volume of signaling IoT devices generate. This is because of the data representation we selected, namely the signaling matrix. We also found that advanced solutions such as the Seq2Seq approach yielded underwhelming results, capturing non-harmful anomalies at a high training and inference cost.

We thus explored the alternative of feature engineering to find a suitable representation for the signaling data available. As previously discussed, feature engineering in the context of network data frequently ends up using only a single modality, typically the quantity. Based on this observation, we chose to evolve the ANCHOR pipeline to rely on a set of carefully engineered features (Deliverable 5.2 [20]) that capture the overall signaling statistics, protocol message types and sequences, or device mobility.

5.2.1.2 Updated ANCHOR Pipeline Design

With ANCHOR, we propose an unsupervised method for anomaly detection of IoT devices, agnostic to device usage. The key idea of our model is to learn the normal network behavior by estimating a low-dimension representation of the signaling messages exchanged by IoT devices. Our final methodology consists of three major steps (Figure 15), which we detail next.

First, we transform the raw data into effective features for the clustering and anomaly detection algorithms described in the following steps. This includes the cleaning and encoding of the data (see the "Creating Features" block in Figure 15).

Figure 15. Model creation pipeline. LR stands for learned representation.

Subsequently, we cluster the devices using overall statistics on the number of daily signaling dialogues, protocol usage, and mobility features. We noticed that sub-groups of devices have very different signaling patterns (see Deliverable 5.2 [20], Section 4.3.2 for more details). Given that our dataset is agnostic to the device purpose (i.e., the IoT vertical application), we propose an unsupervised clustering approach for uncovering the signaling patterns within our dataset. This step is crucial for obtaining a good performance model: if we trained the model with all devices, it would detect the minority class of devices as anomalies because of its different patterns. For example, if we merge signaling logs from many sensors (small amount of signaling logs, massive amount of stationary devices) and few connected cars (larger volume of signaling traffic due to mobility), then an anomaly detection model would always detect the connected cars as anomalies. For each cluster, we apply four anomaly detection models to be compared among them (see "ML Modeling" block in Figure 15). Our models are Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) as a baseline, a Variational Autoencoder (VAE), Isolation Forest, and Tukey fences.

The advanced approach we put forward relies on a likelihood-based model (i.e., bow-tie architecture VAE, as per D4.1 [1]), which consumes the encoded matrices for learning a low-dimension representation of each group of devices. We train the model so that the latent representation effectively represents the normal behavior of devices.

At the inference stage, we compute an anomaly score for each of the devices by comparing new representations to the learned ones. This offers the opportunity to detect anomalies caused by different unknown reasons, indistinct to the device's purpose and without requiring any labeled data.

Feature Engineering. We do feature engineering to transform raw data into effective features for anomaly detection. Our raw dataset includes raw Diameter and MAP dialogues from a sample of approximately four million IoT devices operating worldwide. The dialogues follow the official protocol specifications. We employ the domain knowledge of the IoT Provider operations team to define the per-dialogue protocol fields that best serve the anomaly detection task. The fields we consider include for each SIM the dialogue start date and time, its duration, a format violation indicator (to help eliminate malformed dialogues), the dialogue request type (the operation code such as Send Authentication Information Request (SAIR), or UL request) and the result code (showing whether the request was successful, or it was rejected). We also check the identity of the home and visited operators, and (where available) the identity of the core network elements involved in the signaling dialogue.

We refine our approach in D5.2 [20], and we finally include 95 features, including overall statistics on i) signaling traffic volume, ii) message types and signaling patterns, iii) device activity, iv) mobility statistics, and v) longitudinal activity statistics. The features cover different levels and directions to describe devices as holistically as possible from the point of view of the signaling protocols we monitor. For all features, we consider the period of time of interest (one month in our case), extract the time series of all records for each device per day and compute the statistical features. Our intent is to characterize the overall device behavior and avoid sudden changes and anomalies that may occur on short timescales.

Clustering. The division of managed IoT connectivity service across different domains within the mobile ecosystem, namely, the visited MNO that owns the local radio network, the IoT vertical that uses the radio resource but depends on a different core network that the IoT provider offers, and the roaming hub that interconnects the prior two entities, makes network management, device-level monitoring and anomaly detection a challenging, still unsolved problem. Given our goal to build a solution agnostic to the IoT vertical application using the managed connectivity service, we implement an unsupervised clustering approach to group devices with similar traffic volumes before ingesting them into the anomaly detection pipeline. We use overall statistics (namely, the average over the period of one month we consider) on the number of daily signaling dialogues, protocol usage, and mobility features for clustering. These

features enable us to distinguish between devices serving applications that generate high or low volumes of signaling, devices connecting using 2G/3G or 4G LTE, and stationary or mobile devices, which gives us enough information to divide them into different types of clusters. We generate the clusters using the training data (September 2022). Our clustering model is a GMM with as many components as days in the training dataset (i.e., 30 components if we use a month of data). We select the number of clusters based on homogeneity and volume to avoid very specific clusters with few devices. Namely, we rely on the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) to select the optimal number of clusters.

Table 19. Mean values for the features that distinguish clusters.

Device Cluster	1	2	3	4	5
Overall Statistics: Protocol Usage and Devices					
# Devices	1.7M	420k	894k	300k	621k
# Dialogues per device/day	8.7	22.4	98.4	1300	72
MAP Dialogues (2G/3G) [%]	100	0	99.99	63.4	18.1
Diameter Dialogues (LTE) [%]	0	100	0.01	36.6	81.9
Dialogue Type Volume					
# SAI (2G/3G)	4.2	0	46.4	306	2.1
# SAI (LTE)	0	15	0.01	291	43
# UL (2G/3G)	1.2	0	18.5	145.5	1.1
#UL (LTE)	0	4.4	0.001	244	12.7
# CL (2G/3G)	1.7	0	21.6	117.1	1.6
# CL (LTE)	0	1.2	0.001	102.1	6.5
Mobility Features					
LTE Operator Changes	0	0	0	25	1.6
VLR Changes	2.2	0	36.3	278	1.12
SGSN Changes	1.51	0	20.5	103.8	1

Table 19 gives an overview of the five clusters we identify and their main characteristics. The following five patterns emerge:

- Cluster 1: mostly stationary devices, 2G/3G connectivity only, very low volume of dialogues
- Cluster 2: stationary devices, 4G LTE connectivity only, medium volume of dialogues
- Cluster 3: mildly mobile devices, 2G/3G connectivity, high volume of dialogues
- Cluster 4: highly mobile devices, mixed 2G/3G/4G LTE connectivity, very high volume of dialogues
- Cluster 5: mostly stationary devices, patchy 4G LTE connectivity (with 2G/3G), high volume of dialogues

At inference, we use the previous month of data to assign devices to the generated clusters using the Nearest Neighbor Algorithm, which classifies new devices based on how similar devices (their neighbors) are classified.

Anomaly Detection Models. We use three different unsupervised models on our data: GMM, Isolation Forest, and VAE. Moreover, as a baseline, we also compared against Tukey fences. The unsupervised approach was selected based on the fact that anomalies are, generally, unknown events that are not feasible to train a detection model in a supervised manner.

Tukey Fences: this is also called the box plot rule. It is a simple rule in which the lower quartile (Q1) and the upper quartile (Q3) are considered the *lower_hinge* and *upper_hinge*, respectively, and the difference between the hinges, namely the interquartile range (IQR), is denoted as *H_spread*. Given these variables, two fences are calculated. Any data point beyond those two fence values is considered an anomalous point. This method is particularly useful for visualizing such anomalies in big data.

PCA-GMM: in this method, the features are first transformed into a lower-dimensional representation using PCA, with the aim of retaining as much of the original variance as possible. The reduced data is then clustered using GMM, with the number of components in the mixture determined by the BIC. GMM assumes that regular data is generated from a mixture of Gaussian distributions with unknown parameters. The parameters of the distributions are fit using the expectation-maximization algorithm,

which maximizes the likelihood of the data points. We assign to each data point a probability of being generated by the distribution. If the probability is very low, that is an indication of being an anomaly.

Isolation Forest: the idea behind this algorithm is to isolate the anomalies in a dataset by creating a random forest of isolation trees. An isolation tree is a binary tree that recursively splits the nodes into smaller subsets. The splitting process is based on a randomly selected feature and a randomly selected split value for that feature. The path length from the root node to the terminal node where an instance is isolated is used to calculate an anomaly score. The anomaly score is a number between 0 and 1, and it represents the degree of anomaly of an instance. The closer the score is to 1, the more anomalous the instance is considered to be. The average path length of the trees in the forest is used to determine the threshold value for anomaly detection. The most important parameter in Isolation Forest is called contamination, which is the fraction of the dataset that contains abnormal instances. In ANCHOR, we set this value to 0.1, taking into consideration the size of the operations team, which would need to verify the validity of the anomalies.

FC-VAE: The VAE consists of two sub-networks, namely, an encoder and a decoder. This architecture uses a bottleneck to learn a low-dimensional representation space z of the training data x . The encoder learns the mapping of the input data x into a prior distribution $p(z)$, which is usually a standard Gaussian ($z \sim N(0, I)$). The last layer of the encoder outputs the parameters μ_x, σ_x of the distribution $q(z|x)$. The decoder network is used to reconstruct $\hat{x} \sim p(x|z)$ from the latent representation z sampled from $N(\mu_x, \sigma_x)$. In contrast with the GMM, this model does not make the assumption that data comes from a Gaussian distribution, but it learns the transformation of the data distribution into a Gaussian.

We implemented a fully connected (FC) VAE in which both encoder and decoder networks are composed of 4 fully connected layers with ReLU activation functions. The encoder reduces the number of features up to $z=9$ ($91 \times 64 \times 32 \times 9$), while the decoder does the reverse process, increasing the number of features at each layer ($9 \times 32 \times 64 \times 91$).

5.2.1.3 ANCHOR Usability

In Figure 16, we show the steps for using the final ANCHOR pipeline in a live setting. Namely, as the data for the different roaming hubs is centralized in a data lake, we schedule a daily data extraction in order to get the features that will later be used by the clustering and anomaly detection models. The clustering algorithm will decide to which cluster a particular device belongs. Afterward, we will use the different ML models for a given cluster to create a ranking that indicates how abnormal (i.e., different for the most common devices present in that cluster) that device is behaving. This will be performed daily for each algorithm and each cluster on the data of a given day. This phase generates a list of possible anomalous devices, with their corresponding anomaly score, together with the feature values for such devices. This is, then, the input for the operational team to assess.

Figure 16. Steps for using ANCHOR in a live setting.

We will present our final evaluation results for ANCHOR in cooperation with the Telefonica Global Solution operational team in the upcoming final deliverable for WP5 (D5.3). These results will include the outcome of the pilot we will perform together with TGS for integrating ANCHOR into their system.

5.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

5.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 20. ANCHOR's usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	ANCHOR leverages this interface to receive the monitoring information towards the clustering module and ML modeling blocks of the pipeline.

Nio-Nifcm	ANCHOR uses this interface to orchestrate different parts of the pipeline; for example, it is used to announce the anomaly scores further to the system that the operational teams will verify for further decision-making.
Nifm-Nifnis	ANCHOR uses this interface for standard creation and termination procedures of the NIF instance, e.g., for different IoT clients.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used to interact with the virtualized resources associated with the distributed and centralized NIF operations. Specifically, ANCHOR requires specific resources (i.e., GPU) for training.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used by the ANCHOR controller to trigger re-training of its models and to redistribute them for anomaly detection/inference for each IoT vertical client. This is an on-demand operation based on the NIF performance monitored and reported via the Nio-Nifm interface, such as the anomaly score information monitored and calculated at various timescales.
Mlo-Ncat	This interface allows accessing the model register per different IoT device clusters, thus enabling storage and retrieval of the various models that we include in ANCHOR, such as VAE, PCA-GMM, Isolation Forests, each trained for the different clusters identified.
Nio-Mano	ANCHOR does not use this interface since the results of the anomaly detection are alerting the operational team about potential anomalies in their system.
Nio-Ext	This interface is not used by the NI since the output is not a direct decision but an insight into future anomalies that can be used by the operations teams.

5.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail how this NI solution leverages the NIS creation procedure discussed in Section 5.1.1 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated if a new IoT client buys the managed connectivity service from the IoT platform. The operator then deploys ANCHOR for proactive anomaly detection and improved service to its client. This creates a request to the NIO to fetch a model capable in predicting anomalies for the cluster of devices that includes the IoT vertical of the current IoT client.
2. As these are new IoT devices that were not seen in the network before, the NIO will not find it in the catalog probed via that Nio-Ncat interface.
3. The NIO then triggers a request to retrieve the cluster corresponding to the IoT devices through the Nio-MLp interface. Importantly, the NIO can communicate at this stage important characteristics of the IoT devices that it observed over a 24-hour period, which allows the ANCHOR pipeline to determine the per-device cluster and then use models trained for those respective clusters.
4. Upon training, the model is finally registered in the catalog and made available to the NIO by the MLOps pipeline via the MLp-Ncat and Nio-MLp interfaces, respectively.
5. Finally, the NIO makes NIS/NIF images available to each applicable NIF Component Manager using the Nio-Nifm interface.

5.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 21. Proactive anomaly detection for IoT services in global roaming. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-AARES-000	Effective (90%)	This NI functionality builds an advanced pipeline for anomaly detection in the connectivity of virtually any cellular IoT device.
FR-AARES-001	Effective (90%)	This NI Functionality requires the detection anomaly NIS to be able to operate at different timescales. The ANCHOR pipeline aggregates data at different timescales in order to comply with the capacity of the engineering teams for sifting through the alarms the anomaly detection module generates.
FR-AARES-002	Effective (90%)	This NI functionality depends on high-quality data from the IoT platform, including a sizable amount of historical data to establish normal behavior and ground truth occurrences of anomalies to develop a feasible solution. The ANCHOR pipeline samples data directly from the production IoT platform to then feed it to the anomaly detection pipeline (at different timescales).

FR-AARES-003	Effective (90%)	This NI functionality requires that the anomaly detection model considers the cost of the system in terms of resources for efficient and feasible anomaly detection. In particular, ANCHOR aims to integrate within the production system of the telco; thus, costs around data collection and parsing, model training and inference were considered to design a light solution that fits within the operational budget constraints.
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5.3 Anomaly forecasting in mobile service traffic at base station level

In Section 4.3 of D4.2 [2], we presented an NI to address the problem of anomaly prediction in mobile traffic at the level of individual BSs. Specifically, we consider that the NI must trigger an alarm when an abnormal future traffic load is expected for a specific NSSI. It does so by producing a probability distribution of the traffic demand that the target service will generate in the next time slot at the BS under consideration. The probabilistic prediction is compared against a reference interval that encompasses the expected range of normal traffic values, and if the probability of the anticipated traffic being outside the reference interval is beyond a threshold, an alarm is raised.

5.3.1 Solution description

We refer the reader to Section 4.3 of D4.2 [2] for a complete description of the solution.

5.3.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

5.3.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 22. Anomaly forecasting in mobile service traffic at base station level usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The solutions described above leverage this interface to receive the relevant information about the status of the network. Specifically, relevant metrics that are communicated via Nio-Nifm are the demands recorded at the target BS.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the different components of the algorithm, e.g., the probes to get network information and the API through which the relevant downstream decision-making process is informed of future anomalies.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used for standard creation and termination procedures of NIF instances.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used jointly with the Nio-Nifcm to manage the resources associated to the NI function.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to trigger re-training of the neural network adopted in the solution, typically whenever performance drops below a threshold due to model drifts over time.
Nio-Ncat	This interface allows access to the model register, thus enabling storage and retrieval of trained neural networks. This is important since the solution can be deployed at multiple target BS; hence, a trained model can be used for fast few-shot learning at, e.g., newly deployed BS using models trained on other BS located in similar environments.
Nio-Mano	This interface is not used by the NI since the output is not a direct MANO operation but an insight into future anomalies that can be used by a downstream MANO process.
Nio-Ext	This interface is not used by the NI since the output is not a direct decision but an insight into future anomalies that can be used by a downstream decision-making process.

5.3.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this NI solution leverages the NIS creation procedure discussed in Section 5.1.1 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated if a new BS is deployed and anticipatory anomaly detection must be applied to its demand. This creates a request to the NIO to fetch a model capable of predicting anomalies at the target new BS.
2. As this is a new BS that was not present in the network before, the NIO will not find it in the catalog probed via that Nio-Ncat interface.
3. The NIO then triggers a request to train a new model via the Nio-MLp interface. Importantly, the NIO can communicate at this stage important characteristics of the target BS, such as observed traffic to date or surrounding environment, which allow the MLOps pipeline to use models trained in similar conditions (i.e., at BSs with comparable traffic or surrounding environment) to run a fast few-shot learning on top of neural network architectures already optimized for similar contexts.

4. Upon training, the model is finally registered in the catalog and made available to the NIO by the MLOps pipeline via the MLp-Ncat and Nio-MLp interfaces, respectively.
5. Finally, the NIO makes NIS/NIF images available to each applicable NIF Component Manager using the Nio-Nifm interface.

5.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 23. Anomaly forecasting in mobile service traffic at base station level. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR- AARES-000	Effective (90%)	This NI solution contributes to the overall goal of automating the detection of anomalous behaviors in the mobile network. The specific approach, based on a hybrid forecasting model, is detailed in Section 4.3.3 of D4.2 [2], with accuracy improvements of 25% over state-of-the-art tools, as shown by the evaluations in Section 4.3.3 of D5.2 [20].
FR- AARES-002	Effective (90%)	The predictive anomaly detection NI solution relies on large amounts of historical data to define normal behaviors as baselines, as detailed in Section 4.3.3 of D4.2 [2].
FR-CFORE-004	Successful (100%)	The forecasting model used by this NI solution employs dropout layers to approximate a Bayesian probabilistic output that inherently provides information about the level of accuracy of the prediction, as detailed in Section 4.3.3 of D4.2 [2]. Full validation results in realistic settings are provided in Section 4.3.3 of D5.2 [20].

5.4 Noisy Neighbours in vRANs

5.4.1 Solution description

The computing requirements of a vRAN system are hard to quantify dynamically. To begin with, the amount of CPU resources required by a single vBS instance depends on the network traffic demand on both DL and UL directions, SNR of each wireless link and the associated MCS used for communication, in a non-trivial manner. Moreover, estimating the actual requirements for a set of vBS instances sharing a platform is even more challenging because the overhead introduced by computing resource contention (noisy neighbors) depends on the computing cores used to process each vBS workload, the amount of isolation across vBS instances, and the maximum computing capacity available. On the one hand, over-dimensioning the allocation of computing resources incurs high infrastructure costs as many computing cores might not be needed when running a small number of vBS instances or when the aggregated load is low, and the electricity bill associated with unneeded active cores can be substantial. On the other hand, pooling a reduced number of cores across many instances (i.e., forcing vBSs to share) may lead to throughput loss because heavy resource contention leads to severe computing overheads. Hence, to maximize network performance with minimum infrastructure cost, it is important to tailor the amount of resource isolation appropriately. We design an AI-driven Radio Intelligent Controller (AIRIC) to orchestrate vRAN computing resources. AIRIC relies upon a hybrid neural network architecture combining an RN and a DQN such that: (i) the demand of concurrent virtual base stations is satisfied considering the overhead of noisy neighbors while the operating costs of the vRAN infrastructure are minimized, and (ii) dynamically changing contexts in terms of network demand, SNR and the number of base station instances are efficiently supported.

We consider an O-RAN cloud computing platform (O-Cloud) providing computing resources for multiple vBS instances deployed therein, i.e., each vBS instance shares the same pool of computing resources. We also consider an agent in charge of (i) observing the context associated with each vBS and (ii) devising which computing cores need to be active in the pool to serve the demand of each vBS, which processes uplink and downlink traffic. Following O-RAN's specification, our agent is hosted by the system's SMO and takes decisions in discrete time intervals, which we call decision intervals and are in the range of several seconds to minutes following O-RAN's specification for the Non-RT RIC.

Our agent employs an O-RAN-compliant monitoring system that gathers metrics from the various O-RAN components (such as O-RU, O-DU, and O-CU) and measurements from the O-Cloud platform (i.e., infrastructure metrics). The near-RT RIC uses the E2 interfaces to periodically receive different radio metrics from the components deployed in the O-Cloud platform. Afterward, the near-RT RIC passes the data using the O1 interface to the non-RT RIC. To enforce the different computing policies that our agent computes, it uses the O2 interface to pass those policies to the O-Cloud platform. Given the hard-to-model nature of the noisy neighbor phenomenon, we advocate for reinforcement learning (RL) to design

our agent. In this way, the agent observes the context, takes an action at the beginning of each decision interval, and then receives a reward at the end of the decision interval. The learning agent stores 3-tuple samples comprised of the context, actions, and associated rewards at every interval and uses these experiences to learn and improve the obtained rewards over time.

We do not restrict ourselves to a fixed number of vBSs in the system; instead, we assume a variable number of vBS during each decision interval. A variable number of vBS instances implies that the dimensionality of the context information also varies over time. This is particularly challenging to support with standard RL solutions. To address this, we augment a classical DQN approach with an RN mechanism, as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. AIRIC ML architecture.

We next describe our design for the learning agent's context (states), actions, and reward function.

1. **Context:** we use the following metrics to describe the state:

- a. *Channel Quality:* We use the mean UL SNR observed by each vBS in the last interval, which allows our agent to infer their UL wireless capacity and the mean DL channel quality indicator (CQI) to do the same for the DL.
- b. *Network demand:* The network demand of a vBS is the amount of UE buffered data for both UL and DL during the last decision interval.

We represent DL and UL channel quality for a vBS instance i observed in interval t as $\sigma_{DL,i}^{(t)}$ and $\sigma_{UL,i}^{(t)}$. Furthermore, we let $d_{DL,i}^{(t)}$ and $d_{UL,i}^{(t)}$ denote its DL and UL network demand, respectively. We also assume a known mapping between channel quality and MCS: $g_{DL}(\sigma_{DL,i})$ for DL, $g_{UL}(\sigma_{UL,i})$ for UL, which is a mild assumption. Because the channel quality bounds the highest MCS, we can estimate the mean number of radio Resource Blocks (RBs) that each vBS can use in both directions, given a mean MCS and network demand. This can be estimated using the 3GPP specifications. In this way, we can state the demand for radio RBs rather than relying only on the past utilization of Radio Blocks, which may differ. Consequently, we denote the number of RBs used for DL and UL for vBS i as p_i^{DL} and p_i^{UL} , respectively. Using the number of RBs and network demand, we define vBS i context as

$$\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} = (p_{DL,i}^{(t)}, d_{DL,i}^{(t)}, p_{UL,i}^{(t)}, d_{UL,i}^{(t)})$$

The design of $\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}$ is motivated by the convenience of expressive features and minimal dimensionality and follows the state of the art. The challenge now is to encode the context information $\{\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}\}$ for all vBS instances i in a state vector $\mathbf{s}_i^{(t)}$ with fixed dimensionality D , which is required by the DQN model, in scenarios with a variable number of vBS instances over time. As shown in Figure 17, we address this with an RN.

As the number of vBSs that AIRIC has to allocate CPU resources for in a particular time interval might be different than in past intervals, the context length changes depending on the number of vBS instances. Rather than building other agents for each of the different numbers of vBS cases or padding the various possible contexts to match a fixed context length, we opted to solve the problem using a Relation network. An RN can encode the relationship between the context associated with all vBS instances into a fixed-length state vector $\mathbf{s}_i^{(t)}$.

To this end, the RN operates along all possible pairs of objects (context of vBS instances) to capture such hidden relations with a multi-layered perceptron (MLP) model. Assuming a maximum number of vBS instances supported in the system equal to M , then we have the following possible pairs of context vectors:

$$\chi = \{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2), (\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_3), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_{M-1}, \mathbf{x}_M)\}$$

Since the maximum amount of vBS instances at any given moment is bounded, then $|\chi|$ is also bounded and fixed over time. The RN ingests sequentially each pair $(x_i, x_j) \in \chi$ of possible unpermuted context combinations and generates an output vector $\mathbf{z}_{i,j}$ with cardinality D .

Once all permutation vectors $\mathbf{z}_{i,j}$ are computed by the RN, which is done sequentially, we create an encoded state vector $\mathbf{s}_i^{(t)}$ by aggregating all output $\mathbf{z}_{i,j}$ vectors. In this way, we force order permutation invariance, which is a critical requirement of our problem, i.e., as the RN learns about different latent relations across vBS instances (objects), these learned relations remain invariant regardless of the order of the input pair relations.

Importantly, our RN not only helps to support a variable number of vBS instances over time, but it also provides the DQN model with state information that represents better the relations between them, which is very helpful to capture the impact of noisy neighbors in a state dimension-fixed representation. To this end, we train the RN network jointly with the DQN model.

2. **Actions:** Given state $\mathbf{s}_i^{(t)}$, our agent shall activate the appropriate set of CPU cores, described with an activation vector \mathbf{v} wherein each element corresponds to the CPU core index that shall be activated. Then, all the vBS instances will fairly share the pool of CPU cores in \mathbf{v} . By avoiding pinning vBS workloads into specific cores, we aim at maximizing resource multiplexing and, consequently, at reducing the overall usage of computing resources.

To ensure quick convergence, we need to preserve a low action space dimensionality. To address this, we resolve our action in two steps. In step 1, our RL agent decides the total number of CPU cores that shall be activated to guarantee service. Thus, the set of actions A is $A = \{1, 2, \dots, 2N\}$, where N is the total number of physical cores available. Then, in step 2, we implement a deterministic rule $\rho(a)$ to minimize infrastructure costs. That is, $p: A \rightarrow \mathbf{v}_a$, $a \rightarrow \mathbf{v}$, where \mathbf{v}_a is a set containing all possible activation vectors such that $a = |\mathbf{v}|$

3. **Reward:** Our goal is to meet the traffic demand of all the vBS deployed in the system over time with minimum physical infrastructure (to save costs by turning off CPUs). Assuming a pool with N physical CPUs and $2N$ virtual cores, where cores j and $j + N$ belong to the same physical CPU for all $j < N$, we let $\mathbf{z}(j) \in \{0, \dots, 2N - 1\}$ denote the sibling virtual core i given input virtual core j . A sibling core is one that uses the same physical CPU. We codify the cost associated with an activation vector \mathbf{z} using a linear model. Let us first denote $\mathbf{c}_j^{(t)} \in [0,1]$ as the relative usage of computing core j during interval t . If $j \notin \mathbf{v}^{(t)}$, then $\mathbf{c}_j^{(t)} = 0$; otherwise, $\mathbf{c}_j^{(t)}$ is empirically measured. Then, we let $E_j^{(t)}$ model the (energy-related) cost associated with computing core $j \in \{0,1, \dots, 2N - 1\}$. We now let $\tau_{DL}^{(t)}$ and $\tau_{UL}^{(t)}$ denote the DL/UL throughput experienced by vBS i during interval t , and then formalize our reward function as:

$$\text{If } \tau_{DL,i}^{(t)} < d_{DL,i}^{(t)}, \text{ for any } i, r^{(t)} = -1$$

$$\text{If } \tau_{UL,i}^{(t)} < d_{UL,i}^{(t)}, \text{ for any } i, r^{(t)} = -1$$

$$\text{Otherwise } \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{j=0}^{2N-1} -E_j$$
4. **Training:** The goal is to train a policy to approximate an optimal action-value function Q^* . Our policy π is implemented by the structure of RN+DQN introduced above and, hence, we shall optimize the weights $\theta = (\theta_1, \theta_2)$ of the combined neural networks to estimate the Q-value function $Q(s, a; \theta) \approx Q^*(s, a)$. To this end, we use a Smooth L1-loss function.

To address the noisy neighbor problem in vRANs, we have designed AIRIC, which dimension the computing capacity of a vRAN host, considering the computing overhead introduced by the shared computing platform. AIRIC can adapt to varying contexts, reconfiguring computing platforms dynamically. AIRIC leverages a hybrid learning architecture comprising an RN and a DQN to predict the best hardware configurations over time and counter the vRAN computing platforms sharing adverse effects attaining over the service availability. The experimental evaluation of AIRIC will be presented in deliverable D5.3.

5.4.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

5.4.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 24. AIRIC usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	AIRIC uses this interface to report statistics related to the operation of the different components.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to assign the virtualized infrastructure resources to the AIRIC agent. It is also used to place the corresponding rApp in the domain of the O-RAN Non-RT RIC.

Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used for standard creation and termination procedures of NIF instances.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used to allocate enough computing resources required by the AI model build using an RN and a DQN in AIRIC.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to trigger re-training of the different neural networks adopted in the solution. In the case of having a bigger or smaller number of vBS than the ones already in the model, we have to re-train the model.
Mlo-Ncat	The created models are pushed into the catalog through this interface.
Nio-Mano	Through this interface, the NIO can issue re-orchestration requests to the vRAN system when inference is severely delayed due to a deficit of computing capacity.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with O-RAN components relevant to AIRIC, i.e., the SMO and Non-RT RIC.

5.4.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated when we have to multiplex different vBS using a pool of shared resources that are prone to suffer resource interference due to resource contentions.
2. The NIO looks into the NIS catalog for a trained model. If none exist, a re-training process is triggered.
3. Models are validated and submitted to the O-Cloud, through the Nio-Ext and Nifm-Nifnis interfaces.
4. The O-Cloud system Acknowledges the new parameters.

5.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 25. Noisy Neighbours in vRANs. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-AARES-000	Successful (100%)	AIRIC automatically detects anomalous "noisy neighbors" in RAN virtualization platforms.
FR-AARES-001	Successful (100%)	The operating timescale of AIRIC is configurable by design.

6 Self-learning MANO

In the transition to 5G and 6G, network infrastructure sharing through NFV becomes complex, making manual MANO impractical. In D4.2 [2] we provided solutions regarding placement and scaling. Building on D4.2 [2], we report further advancements in this section.

6.1 Placement and routing new requests

6.1.1 Solution description

In deliverable D4.1 [1], we introduced an RL method to map a (small) service function chain (SFC), modeling a network service or a network slice, on the resources (i.e., the servers and the IP network connecting these servers) of a single datacenter (DC). This RL method took into account a chosen objective and specific constraints. We also compared the performance of this RL method with the traditional approach based on a mixed integer linear program (MILP).

In deliverable D4.2 [2], we introduced a centralized and distributed approach to split a SFC over various data centers, which we compared in deliverable D5.2 [20]. In both cases, we carefully detail which information these approaches have to base their decision on, as it is unrealistic to assume that they will have the full status of all the servers and links in all DCs. The centralized approach was based on a double deep Q-Learning (DDQL) agent, while the distributed approach relied on distributed multi-agent reinforcement learning (DMARL), in which each agent uses DDQL independently.

Here, we briefly describe how both approaches will work together and how they impact the scaling approaches described in Section 6.2. The procedure consists of the following steps:

- Request an end-to-end network service that can be supported by multiple DC
- Split the associated SFC over the available DCs with the method of deliverable D4.2 [2]
- Embed each of the segments of the SFC on servers and links in the assigned DCs
- Life-cycle management with the methods described in Section 6.2.

6.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

These NIFs (as part of the SLMANO NIS) are first created as illustrated in Figure 14 of deliverable D2.3 [3]. Then, they are initialized, as illustrated in Figure 15 of deliverable D2.3 [3], which involves setting up the RL model upon which they are built. From then onwards, they rely on the monitoring capabilities of DAEMON's NI architecture to get the necessary data upon which it bases its segmentation, placement and routing decisions. After initialization, either the NIFs can be (pre)trained offline based on data collected on a digital twin, or they can be directly trained in situ. During both procedures, care needs to be taken to strike the ideal balance between exploitation and exploration. In particular, as the performance of the algorithm gets better, the amount of exploration needs to decrease (to avoid taking too many random decisions). However, if a sudden drop in performance, most probably due to changing circumstances, is detected, the amount of exploration needs to be increased to learn these new circumstances.

6.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 26. Placement and routing new requests usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, the SFC partitioning algorithm (for inter-datacenter partitioning) and the placing/routing algorithm (for intra-data center resource allocation) algorithms discussed in Section 6.1 of this deliverable and in Section 5.1 of D4.2 [2] and in Section 6.1 of D4.1 [1], respectively, report their performance. If the performance degrades, these algorithms need to be retrained. Since these algorithms are based on the reinforcement learning paradigm, the performance can be monitored by tracking the rewards that the decisions the algorithms make. If the rewards drop and this drop is small, a trigger is given to the online reinforcement learning algorithms to increase the temporary exploration ratio. If the drop is substantial, a trigger is given to offline retrain the algorithms on collected data.
Nio-Nifcm	N/A (This interface is not used by these algorithms).
Nifm-Nifnis	Besides the standard creation and termination procedures, this interface is used to update the parameters that determine the partitioning and placement/routing algorithms (i.e., the parameters of the neural network that make the decisions and model the Q-function) after they were retrained.
Nifcm-Nivi	N/A (This interface is not used by these algorithms).

Nio-Mlp	If the drop in performance is small, this interface is not used. If that drop is substantial, through this interface, the necessary data and triggers are given to retrain the partitioning and placement/routing algorithms.
Mlo-Ncat	This interface is used to redeploy retrained algorithms after retraining due to a substantial drop in performance.
Nio-Mano	N/A (This interface is not used by these algorithms).
Nio-Ext	N/A (This interface is not used by these algorithms).

6.1.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail how this classifier uses the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated if the performance of the partitioning or placement/routing drops.
2. If the drop is small, the exploration factor of the algorithm in place is turned up higher so that the algorithms learn online to better match the changing circumstances. If the drop is substantial, these algorithms are retrained offline with the new data, carefully tuning the exploration ratio down as the algorithms learn the new circumstances.
3. In the latter case, the new models are activated through the Nio-Ncat interface.

6.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 27. Placement and routing new requests. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-SLMANO-000	Effective (80%)	Placement/routing of requests for new network services under various traffic loads, as one of the SL MANO components, has been studied in [27] and Section 6.1.4 of D4.1 [1] and [13] and Section 4.4.7 of D5.1 [26], respectively. Random noise was added to the regular patterns, and flash crowds were introduced (see talk on DAEMON's 1 st industrial workshop). Under all circumstances, the components behaved robustly. The status is 30% instead of 100% because, as far as we know, real workloads are not yet available, and the algorithms ideally also need to be tested under those circumstances.
FR-SLMANO-006	Partial (30%)	In the segmentation of SFCs as part of the placement/routing of requests over multiple DCs, as described below, it turned out to be trickier than we initially expected to determine how this balance between exploitation and exploration should be reinstated when the traffic load (drastically) changes. On the one hand, too much exploration results in too many random decisions, while on the other hand, too little exploration risks that the agents get stuck in a suboptimal policy. The status is 30% instead of 100% because the evolution of the exploitation versus exploration balance as of yet was manually tuned. To automatically detect that this balance needs to be revisited (as triggered by a decrease in discounted reward), no properly working solution has been found yet, and it remains a topic that we want to investigate in our future work.
FR-SLMANO-007	Successful (100%)	The placement/routing of requests over multiple data centers (DCs) relies on partitioning service function chains (SFCs). We studied SFC partitioning via a distributed multi-agent reinforcement learning DMARL technique. During the learning phase, we gradually decreased the balance between exploitation and exploration (see Section 4.2.6 of D5.2 [20] and [28]). We chose the decrease in such a way that the system was able to learn the desired behavior.

6.2 Auto scaling

6.2.1 Solution description

In Section 6.2.1 of D4.1 [1], we introduced the VNF scaling problem, which can be solved as a decision-making problem since, for every system interaction, the right number of replicas must be determined to fulfill a given SLA. For that, one of the most used techniques in recent state-of-the-art is RL, as shown in the works [13], [29]–[32].

For instance, in [13], we proposed a control-theoretic solution and a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based scaling solution. Specifically, the reward function of the DRL-based agent was inspired by a popular RL problem called cart-pole. We adapted the reward function defined in the cart-pole problem to fit the scaling problem. The description of the algorithms was provided in Section 6.2 of D4.1 [1], while the comparison between these two agents was shown in Section 4.4.7 in D5.1 [26]. In [29], we introduced a new DRL agent and reward function, this time trying to minimize a cost, defined as a weighted sum. This sum considers the performance and the resource cost and tries to find a balance between the two. The description of the algorithms, as well as the results of the comparison with the control-theoretic solution, are also shown in Section 4.4.7 of D5.2 [20].

In [30], the authors study the impact of microservice interdependencies in auto-scaling mechanisms. They developed gym-hpa, a framework that integrates the popular gym environment developed by OpenAI [33] and the popular Kubernetes (K8s) platform, allowing them to train RL agents on real cloud environments. Similarly, Zalokostas-Diplas et al. [32] compare and evaluate three different scaling algorithms in a real testbed environment and discuss the benefits of ML-driven optimizations against existing state-of-the-art approaches. The authors in [31] proposed a model-based and a model-free RL algorithm for horizontal and vertical auto-scaling in a docker swarm environment. All the works mentioned above demonstrate that ML-based algorithms can achieve better resource utilization and reduce the number of SLA violations when compared to the off-the-shelf K8s Horizontal Pod Autoscaler.

Reproducing the outcomes of an RL algorithm, however, might be much more complicated than expected, as seen in [34]. The authors performed a thorough study where they implemented and compared trendy DRL algorithms in popular benchmarks provided by OpenAI Gym [33], such as half-cheetah, hopper and swimmer. They find out that different implementations of the same algorithm with the same hyperparameters can lead to different behaviors. This reproducibility crisis affects the networking domain much more since the environments are not abstracted to provide common interfaces and performance guarantees are expected from decision-making algorithms since errors and mistakes can have serious economic consequences.

Following this fact and the results obtained in [29], where slightly different reward functions result in quite different scaling behaviors, in this deliverable, we investigate how the reward function definition impacts the behavior of the DRL agents in terms of convergence in learning, how the trained agents behave regarding networking metrics, e.g., computational usage, number of created replicas and fulfillment of the SLAs, and if there are any differencing factors among them. Our goal is to define a methodology for selecting DRL-based autoscaling methods that consider both the behavior and stability of the agent during learning and if this behavior translates into any noticeable impact in the testing phase.

6.2.1.1 Models

In general terms, an MDP is defined as a tuple (S, A, p, r) where S is a set of states, A is a set of actions, p is the transition probability between states s and s' after action a is taken, and r is the immediate reward obtained for performing action a . The policy, defined as π , is a mapping function from states to actions. The solution to an MDP is an optimal policy that maximizes the expected long-term reward, which is a discounted sum of immediate rewards.

RL is a kind of algorithm that can solve MDPs, where an agent explores and analyzes the effects of different actions in an environment. This process can be seen as trial and error, where, after many attempts, the agent learns a strategy that allows it to choose better actions over time. The main element in this learning process is the reward function, which tells the agent if the action it took was appropriate. This function guides the agent towards choosing the actions that maximize an expected (long-term) reward, equivalent to achieving the learning goal [35].

DRL algorithms can be classified as on-policy or off-policy. Off-policy algorithms update their policy using data generated by a different policy. This means that the agent can learn from past experiences and use data collected by any previous policy. On the other hand, on-policy algorithms update their policy while using the data generated by the same policy. This means that the data collected during the learning process is directly used to improve the current policy. As a result, the policy being learned is constantly changing as the agent explores the environment and gathers new experiences.

For this study, we propose two known DRL algorithms that can solve the scaling problem, namely, a DQN and a Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm. DQN is a type of off-policy algorithm that combines Q-learning with deep neural networks to approximate the action-value function, known as the Q-function. Through repeated interactions and learning from the experience replay buffer, the DQN can learn an effective policy to perform well in complex tasks, even in high-dimensional state spaces. It has been successfully applied to various tasks, including playing Atari games and controlling robotic systems. On the other hand, PPO is an on-policy algorithm based on policy gradient that tries to address the limitations of previous policy gradient algorithms, such as TRPO, by striking a balance between making significant updates to the policy (to improve performance) and ensuring that the updates are not too

large, which could lead to instability or catastrophic changes. PPO achieves this by using a "clipped" objective function to update the policy.

Regarding the implementation, we used stable baselines², a popular framework that provides a set of reliable implementations of reinforcement learning algorithms in PyTorch. For both algorithms, we use the default architecture and default hyper-parameters given by stable baselines. To summarize, both algorithms use two fully connected networks with 64 units per layer. While actor and critic are shared for PPO to reduce computation, DQN has separate feature extractors, one for the actor and one for the critic, since the best performance is obtained with this configuration.

6.2.1.2 Reward functions

To guide the agents in their learning, we designed three reward functions.

6.2.1.2.1 *Reward Function 1: Inspired from cart-pole*

This reward function was introduced in Section 5.2.3 of D4.2 [2]. We summarize the reward function definition here for completeness. The reward function is defined in a similar way as in the Cart-Pole problem. More specifically, the reward function at time step t is defined as

$$r(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & |d(t) - d_{tgt}| < \epsilon \cdot d_{tgt} \bigvee |cpu(t) - cpu_{tgt}| < \epsilon \cdot cpu_{tgt} \\ 0 & |d(t) - d_{tgt}| \geq \epsilon \cdot d_{tgt} \bigvee |cpu(t) - cpu_{tgt}| \geq \epsilon \cdot cpu_{tgt} \\ -100 & \text{in episode termination cases} \end{cases}$$

where $d(t)$ is the peak latency from the active VNFs at time step t (taken from the network state), d_{tgt} is the target latency as defined by the SLA and ϵ is a range of tolerance (e.g., 20%). Additionally, we include the CPU usage to avoid the number of instances increasing without control. If the CPU usage is low, probably the workload can be served using fewer VNFs and vice versa. Moreover, the agent is hardly penalized if it incurs a wrong behavior, such as creating more replicas than necessary or exceeding the perceived latency beyond an allowed upper bound.

6.2.1.2.2 *Reward Function 2: A Markov Reward Process*

A Markov Reward Process (MRP) is a mathematical framework used to model and study the behavior of a system that involves stochastic transitions between states and yields rewards over time. MRPs are used to formalize problems where an agent interacts with an environment, and the agent receives rewards for being in certain states, so they could be directly applied to RL setups. An MRP is defined by three main concepts, namely, the states, the transitions, and the rewards. Notice that the states of the MRP could not be the same as in the MDP.

In this case, we define two states: the process exhibits a latency that is *above* the defined threshold, or the process exhibits a latency that is *below* the defined threshold. The transitions between these two states are dictated by the actions that the agent is making. For example, it can be that the process is below the latency threshold, but the agent decides to remove a VNF replica, which takes the process to the state of being above the latency threshold. Then, the designer of the algorithm can clearly establish what are the actions that lead to a good outcome and which do not.

Figure 18. Markov Reward Process for auto-scaling.

Figure 18 shows an example of such MRP. In green are depicted the actions that we considered are good because they lead toward the goal that we want to achieve, i.e., fulfilling the SLA with the least amount of VNF replicas possible. In contrast, depicted in red are the actions that push us away from that goal. More specifically, for both agents, we only reward the good actions. We noticed that by using positive reinforcement, the agents were able to show a better performance. Then, the reward function we used was defined as follows.

² <https://stable-baselines3.readthedocs.io/en/master/index.html>

- If the process is in the state *above*, and the action of the agent is to *increase* the number of replicas, which led to the process being in the *below* state, the agent receives a reward. In this case, the agent is encouraged to increase the number of replicas only to fulfill the SLA.
- If the process is in the state *below*, and the action of the agent is to *decrease* the number of replicas which led to the process being in the *below* state, the agent receives a reward. In this case, the agent is encouraged to be efficient in the use of resources when the SLA is fulfilled.
- All the other combinations of states and transitions are not rewarded nor penalized.

6.2.1.2.3 Reward Function 3: minimizing the weighted sum of the performance and the resource cost

This reward function was introduced in Section 4.4.7 of D5.2 [20]. We summarize the reward function definition here for completeness. The objective of an auto-scaler is to fulfill the agreed SLA with the minimum number of replicas. Therefore, in every time step, the agent pays an immediate cost depending on how good or bad the action it took is. The cost of taking action when the environment moves from one state to another can be defined as a weighted function, including the following contributions.

- If the agent cannot fulfill the SLA, it incurs a performance cost, c_{perf} with an associated w_{perf} , which is paid every time the perceived peak latency (d) exceeds a predefined threshold (d_{max}). The cost is zero otherwise.
- If the agent must deploy a new replica, a resource cost c_{res} is paid, with an associated w_{res} ; this can be seen as a rental cost in cloud environments or the consumed energy of the replica while it is running.

These two contributions are combined into a weighted function, where the respective non-negative weights define an optimization profile, $w_{perf} + w_{res} = 1$. The weights (w_{perf} and w_{res}) multiply an indicator function ($\mathbb{1}\{\cdot\}$) that varies between 1 and -1 depending on whether a condition is met. For instance, if the perceived peak latency is above a threshold, the indicator function is 1; otherwise, it is 0. If a new replica is instantiated, the indicator function is 1 or, if the replica is removed, it is -1. Finally, the reward function is defined as the negative cost function since the main objective is to minimize the total cost.

$$r = -c_{total} = c_{perf} + c_{res} = w_{perf} \cdot \mathbb{1}_{perf} + w_{res} \cdot \mathbb{1}_{res}$$

$$\mathbb{1}_{perf} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d \leq d_{max} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbb{1}_{res} = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if remove replica} \\ 0 & \text{if maintain replica} \\ 1 & \text{if add replica} \end{cases}$$

6.2.1.3 Environment

We developed DynamicSim, a simulator that allows the creation of edge-cloud network scenarios. This simulator is based on Simulation of Discrete Systems of All Scales (Sim-Diasca)³, a general-purpose, parallel, and distributed discrete-time simulation engine for complex systems written in the Erlang language [36]. Erlang facilitates the implementation of large-scale parallel and distributed applications such as the ones tackled in networking. Erlang is a functional programming language based on the actor model, a powerful model for creating highly concurrent, distributed software. Each actor in this architecture is considered a processing unit, which can communicate with other actors via asynchronous messages. Each actor stores their respective messages that are pending processing. After processing the message, an actor modifies its state, sends more messages, or makes new actors. Due to the actors' lack of shared state or resources and the asynchronous nature of all communication, this paradigm significantly reduces blocking waits and race situations, two major issues with concurrent systems. Moreover, the actor model facilitates the development of distributed software since it makes no difference if two actors are running on the same machine or on different ones. However, the language based on the actor model must implement a communication model that permits message exchange between actors running on various machines.

Figure 19 shows the architecture of the simulator. Sim-Diasca (lower layer) is in charge of synchronizing time between the actors, evolving the system state, sending and receiving messages to and from the controller (i.e., decision-making agent), and managing the results. Its built-in support for distributed simulation enables deploying a simulation case over multiple computers. Through the base actor model, own-defined models can be created. Therefore, we establish the middle layer called DynamicSim, in which we define an actor model for the VNFs, the server, and the load balancer. The traffic generator and the monitor modules act as an interface between the actors in the lower layer and the high-level

³ <https://github.com/Olivier-Boudeville-EDF/Sim-Diasca>

functions defined in Python through the sub-pub communication schema developed by ZeroMQ. Finally, we design several user-defined simulation cases in the topmost layer, including the one presented in the previous section.

Figure 19. Architecture of Sim-Diasca.

6.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

In this subsection, we detail how this solution leverages the **NIF management procedure** discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3]. The scaling solution described in the previous subsection can be divided into different NIF-C, how it was shown in D4.2, section 5.2.4 [2]. Therefore, we assume that all the NIF-Cs are already deployed and that an NIF and NIF-C Manager are in place.

6.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 28. DRL-based autoscaler's usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The DRL-based scaler reports the immediate reward, the cumulated reward, or the average reward from the last iterations. This value can be set according to the operator's needs. With this information, NIO's monitoring block can track the health of the model and timely trigger NI management procedures.
Nio-Nifcm	Thanks to this interface, the scaling decisions can effectively be communicated to the manager of the infrastructure.
Nifm-Nifnis	In case the scaler should track more than one SLA, multiple versions of the scaler could be deployed, configuring a multi-agent setup. Consequently, the decisions to scale and place the new agents should be communicated using this interface.
Nifcm-Nivi	N/A. The decisions of the scalers are communicated using the Nio-Nifcm interface.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to train new ML-based models for autoscaling.
Mlo-Ncat	The alternative models, e.g., other ML-based models or traditional algorithms, are stored in the catalog so that NIO can easily replace them. They are exchanged using this interface.
Nio-Mano	This interface should be used in case MANO is deployed as an external entity. In this case, the NIO instructs MANO on the scaling decisions made by the DRL-based scaler. Otherwise, the interface is not used since NIO takes the functions of MANO.
Nio-Ext	This interface could be used in case multiple scalers are deployed across multiple domains.

6.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

The management procedure is initiated when the NIO detects that the reward function of the DRL-based auto-scaler is showing a constant decay.

1. The NIO's monitoring block reports the decaying of the reward function, which implies a deterioration in the scaler's performance. Then, the NIO triggers a management procedure (the NI needs to be handled) using the Nio-MLp and the Mlo-Ncat interfaces.

2. Since the RL can be seen as an online algorithm, the reason for the model to underperform is not associated with data shifts but more related to the model itself, e.g., the architecture does not support the dimensionality of the incoming data, or the reward function does not reflect newly set objectives or boundaries. Then, most likely, a retraining of the scaler model is not enough to solve the problem. Thus, NIO should directly look for an alternative model that suits the new conditions. Model selection should be performed in case there is more than one model available.
3. In case there is no alternative model, then the NIO triggers retraining using the Nio-Mlp interface.
4. The resulting model is uploaded to the NIF Manager by using the Nio-Nifm interface, acknowledging the upload and deploying the new model in a posterior step.

Notice that scaling itself is a management operation. In contrast, the procedure described above attains the DRL-scaler and its performance, thus, the management of the NI. Typical MANO operations can be followed when the scaler decision implies the management of VNFs, as shown in [37].

6.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 29. DRL-based autoscaler. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3 [3]	Status	Discussion
FR-MTERM-006	Successful (95%)	Briefly summarize the requirement, then describe in a qualitative way how the design of the solution allows to achieve the requirement. Reference the relevant sections in this document and in the previous deliverables, D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [1]. The multi-timescale resource management NI proposed by DAEMON will use NIFs and NISs to support the orchestration of edge resources. Being scaling one critical MANO operation, designing better scaling solutions directly impacts the performance of the NI. The benchmarking described in this deliverable allows for designing better scaling solutions that take business and operational KPIs into account. With the updates made in this deliverable, the scaling solution described in Section 6.2.1 is completed, which updates the status of the requirement from 90% [3] to 95%.
FR-MTERM-007	Successful (95%)	The NI proposed by DAEMON shall provide automated on-the-fly reconfiguration of VNFs. The scaling solution proposed in this deliverable does not require complete re-training to learn new patterns when the workload or the SLA changes. Moreover, the reward function guides learning by determining the actions that reach the (multi-)objective function. In each state, the DRL-based scaler can find the action that suits that state; thus, we are not instructing the scaler what action to take; instead, the scaler takes that decision autonomously, following a learned strategy. With the updates made in this deliverable, the scaling solution described in Section 6.2.1 is completed, which updates the status of the requirement from 85% [3] to 95%.
FR-SLMANO-003	Successful (100%)	Through this NI, controllers and orchestrators should converge to stable control loops. The reward functions defined in this deliverable guide the DRL-based scaler to stable behaviors, as shown in [13] and [29]. With the updates made in this deliverable, the scaling solution described in Section 6.2.1 is completed, which updates the status of the requirement from 90% [3] to 100%.

7 Outlook towards 6G

The solutions outlined in this deliverable have been coordinated, either directly or indirectly, with the ongoing initiative to define and subsequently establish standards for the 6G mobile system, especially the standards for Natively Intelligent Networks [38]. In particular, we present a novel data-centric Service Based Architecture in the following and demonstrate how DAEMON is aligned with 6G standardization for this specific solution.

7.1 Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network

The emergence of 5G networks marked a significant departure from the conventional network approach, shifting from the point-to-point model seen in earlier generations to a Service-Based Architecture (SBA) that emphasizes a Cloud-native design. In this transition, the SBA was primarily viewed as a centralized hub with a single administrative domain.

Looking ahead to the arrival of 6G, there is a renewed focus on refining the SBA model, with the goal of expanding End-to-End (E2E) orchestration into the far-edge domain. This expansion includes embracing serverless computing, thereby transforming it into a fully decentralized system.

In anticipation of the forthcoming 6G era, ZSCALE introduced a pioneering data-centric interaction framework. This framework is structured as a dataflow, utilizing serverless atomic functions, and it represents a reimagining of the existing control-plane core network principles and processes [39]. This innovative approach offers several advantages, including:

- **Streamlined Core Network Signaling:** The atomic nature of functions and their ability to be assembled into dataflow graphs contribute to more efficient signaling. This results in faster procedures and reduced message overhead.
- **Simplified Refactoring:** Location transparency and data-focused primitives enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of shipping software updates, especially in light of the increasing trend toward software-driven decentralization in 6G networks.
- **Serverless, Stateless, Reusable, and Shareable Functions:** Viewing atomic functions and their composition as a dataflow graph built on data-centric fundamentals enables the creation of stateless functions that can be dynamically shared and replicated across volatile resources in a serverless manner.
- **End-to-End Orchestration Across the Spectrum:** Given the inherent heterogeneity of 6G networks, a service data-flow approach offers a unified method for managing and orchestrating finely-grained services spanning multiple administrative domains.
- **Enhanced Security and Fault Tolerance:** A data-centric and dataflow-oriented approach provides security and fault tolerance at the content level. It secures connections by leveraging TLS and mutual TLS authentication, along with access control, to ensure hop-to-hop security.

In general, DAEMON can benefit from such proposed solutions that could be integrated with the NI platform to support flexible service routing and discovery capabilities, to simplify the development of service functions and to enable the execution of NI algorithms with full utilization of the distributed resources available over multiple infrastructures across the continuum.

8 Conclusions

Deliverable D4.3 presented the progress on the 14 NI solutions, with 13 of them initially reported in D4.1 [1] and 1 of them introduced in D4.2 [2]. We discuss the developments for each Task, which materialize ideas and satisfy the requirements identified in WP2. Furthermore, we describe the integration of each solution into the NI plane as outlined in Deliverable D2.3 [3]. We also include a discussion on the integration of solutions that have been fully described in the previous deliverables. We present the progress of the solutions that include energy-aware VNF orchestration in open-source MANO infrastructure with improved forecasts, two novel approaches for energy-focused vRAN orchestration mechanisms, and improved performance with a novel cost function for energy-driven joint vRAN and edge service orchestration for different application-specific performance KPIs in Task 4.1. Moving to Task 4.2, we report the progress on anticipatory capacity allocation that allows the joint optimization of admission control and resource allocation and improves the optimistic learning framework that utilizes the predictions and is able to produce discrete decisions. In the context of Task 4.3, we have addressed multiple challenges in federated learning techniques for anomaly detection in cellular networks, improved the performance of proactive anomaly detection solutions for large IoT systems with feature engineering, and developed a hybrid algorithm consisting of RN and DQN for the noisy neighbor problem in virtualized computing platforms (O-RAN) from the perspective of anomaly detection. Finally, Task 4.4 explains the methodology that allows the approaches defined previously to work together. Both approaches target MANO-type solutions for B5G systems.

The presented results are detailed and supported by rigorous analytical models and/or data-driven (ML-based) techniques. Their development involved close collaboration across different work packages, including extensive discussions to satisfy and revisit the operational requirements stated in WP2. Evaluations and assessments of these solutions within the context of WP5 were also conducted. During the preparation of this deliverable, the consortium engaged in regular discussions and internal workshops to iterate among requirements, proposed solutions, and their evaluation before finalizing the ideas presented in this document. A critical approach was taken throughout the development of these solutions, in line with the manifesto and mission of DAEMON. This involved assessing the limitations of AI and proposing remedies when identified. For instance, we have shown that poorly selected features can hinder the performance of the solution and improved the solution in Section 5.2 by adding a feature engineering step. In addition, we modified the solutions to fit more in real-world scenarios by including novel cost functions (Section 3.4) and allowing our solutions to produce discrete decisions as well as continuous decisions (Section 4.4).

Through the requirements and integration parts, we finalized the solutions and presented them as a fully integrated NI plane.

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